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International Symposium On Metal Complexes (24-28 June - Wrocław)

Acta of the International Symposia on Metal Complexes

University of Wrocław (POLAND)

ISMEC 2015
24-28 JUNE, WROCLAW, POLAND

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Faculty of Chemistry, University of Wrocław, Wrocław, Poland.
President of the Scientific Committee of ISMEC2015

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We have the great pleasure of welcoming you in Wrocław, for the XXVIth International Symposium on Metal Complexes (ISMEC2015). The 2015 edition of ISMEC proudly continues the tradition of previous ISMECs and Italian-Spanish Congress on Thermodynamics of Metal Complexes, since its origins was held alternatively either in Italy or in Spain.

The meeting is focused on different aspects of the study and application of thermodynamics of metal complexes in the fields of Analytical, Biomedical, Environmental, Inorganic and Physical Chemistry, in particular focusing on topics such as:

Chemical thermodynamics
Solution equilibria and coordination chemistry
Metal-complex interactions with biomolecules
Metals in diseases: transport, homeostasis and toxicity
Metal-based drugs: therapy and diagnosis
Analytical methods and sensors, based on metal complexes
Nanostructured metal complexes
Proteomics and metabolomics
Metals in supramolecular chemistry
Computer methods for equilibrium analysis

The present edition of ISMEC is held from 24th June to 28th June 2015 in Wrocław (Poland) and is organized by Prof. Henryk Kozłowski and the members of his team: DSc. Elżbieta Gumienna-Kontecka, Dr. Magdalena Rowińska-Żyrek and Dr. Marek Łuczkowski.

Since 2011, immediately after each symposium, “*Acta of ISMEC Symposia*” is published. The aim of this series is a quick disclosure of the most recent advances of scientific research in the field of thermodynamics of metal complexes. Every book of the series is edited both by the President of the Scientific Committee of each ISMEC edition in collaboration with the President of ISMEC Group.

We are confident we will be able to provide you with an exciting scientific event, featuring outstanding international speakers and a remarkable atmosphere. We wish you enjoyable stay in Wrocław.

**Henryk Kozłowski
and Enrique García-España**

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Wednesday, 24th

14:00-17:00

Registration

The Main Edifice of the University of Wrocław (Plac Uniwersytecki 1)

17:00-17:30

Opening Ceremony

Henryk Kozłowski, head of the University of Wrocław Bioinorganic Chemistry Group

Adam Jezierski, Vice-Rector of the University of Wrocław for Research and International Relations,

The Main Edifice of the University of Wrocław (Plac Uniwersytecki 1)

Chairperson: *Guido Crisponi*

17:30-18:10 PL-1

Enzo Alessio, Trieste, Italy *'Development of new water-soluble metal complexes as precursors for the preparation of metal-porphyrin conjugates for medicinal and supramolecular chemistry'*

18:15

Welcome Reception

The Main Edifice of the University of Wrocław (Plac Uniwersytecki 1)

Thursday, 25th

Chairperson: *Magdalena Rowińska-Żyrek*

9:00-9:40

PL-2

Daniela Valensin, Siena, Italy *'Membrane interactions and the effect of metal ions of amyloidogenic proteins'*

9:40-10:00

INV-1

Józef Lewandowski, Warwick, United Kingdom *'Application of paramagnetic metal complexes to study structures and dynamics of protein complexes in the solid state'*

10:00-10:20

INV-2

Olga Iranzo, Marseille, France *'Short His-containing peptides: versatile tools to design similar copper(II) complexes with different properties and redox behaviors'*

10:20-10:40

INV-3

Maurizio Remelli, Ferrara, Italy *'The hemoglobin fragment AGHLDDLPGALSAL: complex-formation properties and biological activity'*

10:40-11:00

INV-4

Anna Peacock, Birmingham, Edgbaston, United Kingdom *'New ligands for "non-biological" metal ions and new applications for metalloproteins'*

11:00-11:30

Coffee break

Chairperson: *Antonio Bianchi*

11:30-12:00

KN-1

Thomas Ward, Basel, Switzerland *'Artificial metalloenzymes: challenges and opportunities'*

12:00-12:15

OC-1

Joanna Wątył, Wrocław, Poland *'Poly-His protein fragments from snake venoms as unusual domains in metal ion binding'*

12:15-12:30

OC-2

Mari Shimura, Tokyo, Japan *'Visualization of intracellular metals by scanning X-ray fluorescence microscopy- application for cell biology and medicine'*

12:30-12:45 OC-3 **Véronique Patinec**, Brest, France '*Contribution of thiazolyle arms in the stability of Cu(II)/Cu(I) polyazacycloalcanane-based chelates for PET imaging*'

12:45-13:00 OC-4 **Helmut Sigel**, Basel, Switzerland '*Metal ion-binding properties of the monoprotonated phosphonate residue of 9-[2-(phosphonomethoxy)ethyl]-2-amino-6-dimethylaminopurine (PME2A6DMAP). A model for the metal ion affinity of phosphoryl-diester bridges*'

13:00-15:00

Lunch

Chairperson: *M. Amelia Santos*

15:00-15:15 OC-5 **Premysl Lubal**, Brno, Czech Republic '*Thermodynamic, kinetic and structural study of transition metal complexes of NOTA ligand*'

15:15-15:30 OC-6 **Michel Meyer**, Dijon, France '*New thermodynamic and structural insights into plutonium(IV) complexation with open chain and cyclic polyaminocarboxylic acids*'

15:30-15:45 OC-7 **Yan Voloshin**, Moscow, Russian Federation '*Design of cage metal complexes as topological drugs, antifibrillogenic agents, paramagnetic and luminescent probes*'

15:45-16:05 INV-5 **Jerzy Lisowski**, Wrocław, Poland '*Metal complexes of large chiral macrocycles*'

16:05-16:25 INV-6 **Enrique García-España**, Valencia, Spain '*Molecular self-assembling mediated by pyrazole macrocycles*'

16:25-16:55 KN-2 **Peter Comba**, Heidelberg, Germany '*Bispidine coordination chemistry: fundamental principles and applications in medicinal chemistry, bioinorganic modeling and oxidation catalysis*'

16:55-17:25

Coffee break

Chairperson: *Peter Gans*

17:25-17:40 OC-8 **Paulina Kolkowska**, Wrocław, Poland '*The role of the HypA loop sequence in binding Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺*'

17:40-18:10 KN-3 **Shun Hirota**, Takayama, Ikama, Japan '*Cytochrome c and myoglobin oligomers formed by domain swapping*'

18:10-18:50 PL-3 **Bernard Meunier**, Toulouse, France '*A specific copper chelator as drug candidate for Alzheimer's disease*'

19.00-20.00

GTC Meeting

Friday, 26th

Chairperson: *Juan Nicolás Gutierrez*

9:00-9:40 PL-4 **Edit Y. Tshuva**, Jerusalem, Israel '*Anticancer Ti(IV) complexes of polydentate phenolato chelates: able and stable, effective and selective*'

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|-------------|-------|--|
| 9:40-10:10 | KN-4 | Dan Gibson , Jerusalem, Israel <i>'Dual targeting Pt(IV) anticancer agents'</i> |
| 10:10-10:30 | INV-7 | Daniela Donghi , Zürich, Switzerland <i>'Platinum binding to RNA: interaction of oxaliplatin with an RNA internal loop'</i> |
| 10:30-10:50 | INV-8 | Athanasios Salifoglou , Thessaloniki, Greece <i>'Vanadium metallodrugs in cancer therapeutics. A molecular approach'</i> |
| 10:50-11:10 | INV-9 | Alicia Dominguez-Martin , Zürich, Switzerland <i>'Towards understanding the folding dynamics of the G-quadruplex sequence at the 5'-UTR of the human BCL2 mRNA'</i> |

11:10-11:30

Coffee break

11:30-13:00

Poster Session

13:00-15:00

Lunch

Free afternoon

Saturday, 27th

Chairperson: *Nicolás Veiga*

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|-------------|--------|---|
| 9:00-9:40 | PL-5 | Merce Capdevila , Barcelona, Spain <i>'Metallothioneins: balancing the inorganic and biological worlds'</i> |
| 9:40-10:00 | INV-10 | Nils Metzler-Nolte , Bochum, Germany <i>'to be announced soon'</i> |
| 10:00-10:20 | INV-11 | Raffaella Biesuz , Pavia, Italy <i>'Solid phase equilibria: our story, past, present and future'</i> |
| 10:20-10:40 | INV-12 | Noráh Barba-Behrens , Mexico, Mexico <i>'Structural, electronic, magnetic and biological properties of coordination compounds withazole derivatives'</i> |
| 10:40-11:00 | INV-13 | Joanna I. Lachowicz , Cagliari, Italy <i>'The copper and zinc chelation side effect of some drugs for diabetic patients'</i> |

11:00-11:30

Coffee break

Chairperson: *Tarita Biver*

- | | | |
|-------------|--------|---|
| 11:30-11:50 | INV-14 | Luigi Messori , Sesto Fiorentino, Italy <i>'to be announced soon'</i> |
| 11:50-12:05 | OC-9 | Ester Vilchez-Rodriguez , Granada, Spain <i>'A novel ternary complex emphasizes the depletion of basicity in the N3-acyclovir donor atom within the main Cu(II)-acyclovir binding pattern'</i> |
| 12:05-12:20 | OC-10 | Agnieszka Chylewska , Gdańsk, Poland <i>'Novel dual band acid-base indicators based on Ni(II) or Cu(II) coordination compounds with vitamin B₆'</i> |
| 12:20-12:35 | OC-11 | Lluís Guisjarro Ferrer , Paterna, Spain <i>'Synthesis and metal ion complexation studies of new polytopic aza-scorpion receptors'</i> |

12:35-12:50 **OC-12** **Demetrio Milea**, Messina, Italy '*Binding ability of diethylenetriamine-N,N,N',N",N"-pentakis-(methylenephosphonic) acid toward biologically, environmentally and technologically relevant cations*'

13:00-15:00

Lunch

Chairperson: **Zyta Ziara**

15:00-15:15 **OC-13** **Natalia Busto**, Burgos, Spain '*DNA binding and nuclease activity of two quinones and their ruthenium complex counterparts*'

15:15-15:30 **OC-14** **Lucía Otero**, Montevideo, Uruguay '*Homo- and heteroleptic metal complexes of bisphosphonates targeting enzymes of the isoprenoid biosynthetic pathway and/or DNA*'

15:30-15:50 **INV-15** **Tamas Gajda**, Szeged, Hungary '*Metal ion complexes of some tren- and tach-based tripodal ligands*'

15:50-16:10 **INV-16** **Andrea Melchior**, Udine, Italy '*Speciation and structure of the Ni(II)/nitrate system in bumimTf2N ionic liquid*'

16:10-16:30 **INV-17** **Manuel Valiente**, Barcelona, Spain '*Cooperation between EU and MED countries in science and technology. Project FP4BATIW as an example for cooperation in water characterization and treatment*'

16:30-16:40 **Pulidori Award** Maurizio Remelli

16:40-17:00 **OC-15** **Matteo Savastano**, Florence, Italy '*Metal complexes of polyazamacrocyclic ligands as surface functionalities of multi-walled carbon nanotubes*'

17:00-17:20

Coffee break

Chairperson: **Elżbieta Gumienna-Kontecka**

17:20-18:00 **PL-6** **Christoph Fahrni**, Atlanta, United States of America '*Illuminating biological trace metals: from single cells to whole organisms*'

18:00-18:30 **Closing & ISMEC 2016 Presentation**

20:00

Banquet

PLENARY LECTURES

Development of new water-soluble metal complexes as precursors for the preparation of metal-porphyrin conjugates for medicinal and supramolecular chemistry

Federica BATTISTIN, Elisabetta IENGO, Enzo ALESSIO

Department of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Trieste, Via L. Giorgieri 1, 34127 Trieste (Italy); alessio@units.it

The aim of our research is that of developing novel metal complexes – in particular of Ru(II) and Re(I) – to be used as precursors in the synthesis of metal-porphyrin conjugates. Figure 1 reports the schematic structure of a generic metal-porphyrin conjugate.

Figure 1. A generic metal-porphyrin conjugate.

Such conjugates might find application in the field of medicinal chemistry as multimodal agents, i.e. compounds that combine in a single molecule the modalities of imaging and therapy [1-3]. For example, a Ru-porphyrin conjugate might combine the phototoxicity and the tumor-localization properties of the porphyrin with the cytotoxicity of the metal fragment for additive antitumor effects, and the emission of the chromophore can be exploited for tracking the biodistribution of the adduct at the cellular level through fluorescence microscopy. Conjugation of the porphyrin with Re/^{99m}Tc congeners would provide a *matched pair* of compounds: the non-radioactive (*cold*) Re conjugate for chemical investigation, fluorescence imaging and photodynamic therapy (PDT), and the gamma-emitting (*hot*) ^{99m}Tc conjugate potentially suitable for bimodal molecular imaging (fluorescence and SPECT).

In addition, metal-porphyrin conjugates are investigated also in different fields, such as in the construction of supramolecular assemblies for photocatalysis and molecular recognition [4,5].

The porphyrin needs to be connected to the metal fragment through a bifunctional chelating agent, a *linker*, i.e. a molecule with two functional groups – that typically point in opposite directions: one functional group (e.g. a -COOH) must be capable of making an organic bond with the photosensitizer (e.g. an amidic or esteric bond), the other must be suited for binding the metal fragment.

Therefore, in the **ideal metal precursor** the number and geometry of the binding sites (i.e. relatively labile leaving ligands, such as dmsO, CH₃CN or Cl⁻) have to match exactly the binding preferences of the linker connected to the photosensitizer. The other ancillary ligands on the metal are inert, most often chelates, in order to afford thermodynamic and kinetic stability. In addition, ligands are selected with the aim of keeping the geometry of the metal fragment as symmetrical as possible, in order to limit the formation of stereoisomeric products upon binding of the linker. Finally, since solubility of the conjugates in aqueous solution is a primary goal, at least one coordination position will be occupied by highly hydrophilic ancillary ligands such as 1,3,5-triaza-7-phosphadamantane (PTA, Figure 2).

In this lecture I will report our most recent results on the chemistry of Ru(II)-PTA precursors and their reactivity towards diimine linkers such bpyAc and cppH (Figure 2) [6].

Figure 2. Schematic structures of the hydrophilic ligand PTA and of the bidentate linkers bpyAc and cppH.

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Membrane Interactions and the effect of metal ions on amyloidogenic proteins

Daniela Valensin,^{a)} Riccardo De Ricco,^{a)} Caterina Migliorini,^{b)} Marek Luczkowski,^{b)} Aleksandra Hecel,^{b)} Henryk Kozłowski,^{b)}

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Understanding the mechanisms of neurodegenerative diseases represents nowadays an increasingly growing issue in medical biological and chemical research. Neurodegenerative diseases damage central nervous system of many mammals species and their pathogenesis has been associated with proteins misfolding and proteinaceous aggregates accumulating in neuronal cells. The major hallmark of these pathologies is the presence of inclusion bodies mainly made of protein aggregates in the brain, consisting of fibers assembled by misfolded proteins with β -sheet conformation. Amyloid β (A β), alfa Synuclein (α S) and human Prion Protein (hPrP) are the amyloidogenic proteins associated to Alzheimer Disease, Parkinson Disease and Transmissible Spongiform Encephalopathies respectively. All these proteins are entirely or partially unfolded and they are prone to aggregation in the human body as well as in vitro conditions. On the other hand, they undergoes to α -helix structural transition in presence of membrane mimicking environments [see for example refs 1-3].

Transition metals ions, like copper, zinc and iron play very important role in neurodegeneration having impact on both protein structure and oxidative stress. Interestingly A β , α S and hPrP exist in copper-metallated forms and a huge number of evidence has pointed out that specific binding domains exist for both Cu(II) and Cu(I) oxidation states [see for example refs 4-7].

In this study, we investigated how the α -helix structural transition affects Cu(II) and Cu(I) binding to amyloidogenic proteins with the final aim to determine the structural and thermodynamic features of the metal complexes. The effects of either copper binding or membrane interactions on the structural rearrangements of amyloidogenic peptides, derived from A β , α S and hPrP proteins, are discussed [8-12].

Financial support by PRIN (Programmi di Ricerca di Rilevante Interesse Nazionale) (2010M2JARJ_004), CIRMMP (Consorzio Interuniversitario Risonanze Magnetiche di Metalloproteine Paramagnetiche) and CIRCMSB (Consorzio Interuniversitario di Ricerca in Chimica dei Metalli nei Sistemi Biologici) is gratefully acknowledged.

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Anticancer Ti(IV) Complexes of Polydentate Phenolato Chelates: Able and Stable, Effective and Selective

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Titanium(IV) complexes are promising candidates for anticancer chemotherapy as alternatives for cisplatin and other platinum-based drugs. A main advantage of the titanium metal is its biocompatibility; titanium oxide, the final decomposition product of titanium(IV) complexes in water environment, is often present in food and cosmetic products and has no known side effects. Titanium(IV) based compounds that previously reached clinical trials showed wider activity range and reduced toxicity relative to cisplatin, but readily decomposed in water environment thus inhibiting mechanistic analysis and practical utility.

We have introduced the phenolato titanium(IV) complexes as superior anti-tumor agents.^[1-5] Compounds of this type showed activity higher than that of cisplatin toward a variety of human cancer cell lines, including toward cells resistant to cisplatin and other drugs, with marked selectivity to cancerous cells. Importantly, enhanced hydrolytic stability was achieved for various derivatives, where in fact, leading compounds showed no decomposition for weeks in water, while maintaining high anti-cancer activity both *in vitro* and *in vivo*.

Herein, the tale on the design and developmental stages for several generations of compounds will be overviewed, along with the insights gained throughout, directing the research paths to the current state of knowledge. Structure-activity relationships will be presented, along with mechanistic insights on the compounds activity in the cell, including the nature of the active species and possible cellular targets.

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Metallothioneins: balancing the inorganic and biological worlds

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Metallothioneins (MTs) were discovered in the 50s when looking for a Cd²⁺-binding protein in mammalian (horse) kidney. Since then, this ubiquitous and very big family of proteins that are characterized by their high capability for heavy metal ion coordination (metallo-) and elevated sulfur, *i.e.* Cys, content (-thioneins) has attracted much attention, being the protagonist of thousands of scientific papers [1]. Initially, MTs were exclusively considered as detoxifying agents against toxic metal ions. Afterwards, they have been related to many physiological events that include from the homeostatic control on Zn(II) and Cu(I) essential elements, until the control of redox processes and oxidative stress, among others. Nowadays, their functionality in living organisms is still a matter of debate. Our group has been involved in the study of MTs since the beginning of the 90s. During this almost 25 years of research we have analyzed the properties, and more specifically the metal-binding abilities, of a considerable number of MTs belonging to the most diverse organisms scattered through the Tree of Life [2]. The rigorous application of the same methodology for MT synthesis and analysis [3], has allowed the comparison of all the gathered results in a wide frame and rendered a more comprehensive picture of the properties of the whole family. This has allowed us not only to propose a new classification of their members following a gradation between genuine Zn-thioneins and clear Cu-thioneins, but it has also revealed many different peculiarities of the constituents of this family of metalloproteins that entitle us to state that much remains still to be studied and discovered about MTs. Some particular examples will be provided that will enlighten these affirmations as well as a spotlight in our latest and more interesting findings.

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Illuminating Biological Trace Metals: From Single Cells to Whole Organisms

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The identification and quantification of transition metals, ideally in the context of their native physiological environment, is of critical importance for a comprehensive understanding of metal homeostasis in cells, tissues, and whole organisms. To this end, we developed a suite of molecular tools for interrogating the nature of labile copper and zinc pools within a biological context. Systematic optimization of the ligand structure and fluorophore properties were key for creating a Cu(I)-selective fluorescent probe [1] that combines a 180-fold fluorescence contrast with a limit of detection in the sub-parts-per-trillion concentration range. A series of water-soluble affinity standards were developed for probing the interaction of Cu(I) with proteins, peptides, and small molecule ligands under physiologically relevant conditions [2]. The affinity standards were instrumental in elucidating the nature of the glutathione-Cu(I) system and revealed the formation of tetranuclear Cu(I)-clusters with a buffering ability in the subfemtomolar concentration regime. Furthermore, a Zn(II)-selective emission ratiometric probe was optimized for two-photon excitation microscopy and employed for imaging the dynamics of Zn(II) fluxes in live cells and developing zebrafish embryos. As a complementary approach we utilized synchrotron X-ray fluorescence microscopy and microtomography to visualize the transition metal distribution in proliferating cells and zebrafish embryos [3]. Together, the studies imply critical physiological roles of copper and zinc in development that differs from their established functions as cofactors in metalloproteins or as messengers in signaling pathways. In summary, the combination of molecular tools and advanced X-ray fluorescence imaging techniques represents a powerful approach towards advancing our understanding of metal homeostasis in biology.

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KEYNOTES LECTURES

Artificial Metalloenzymes: Challenges and Opportunities

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Artificial metalloenzymes result from incorporation of a catalytically competent organometallic moiety within a host protein. We and others have been exploiting the potential of the biotin-(strept)avidin technology for the creation of artificial metalloenzymes, Figure. Thanks to the remarkable supramolecular affinity of biotin for either avidin or streptavidin ($K_D > 10^{-13}$ M), linking of a biotin anchor to a catalyst precursor ensures that, upon stoichiometric addition of (strept)avidin, the metal moiety is quantitatively incorporated within the host protein.

Such artificial metalloenzymes are optimized either by chemical (variation of the biotin-spacer-ligand moiety) or genetic- (mutation of (strept)avidin) means. These chemogenetic schemes were applied to optimize the performance for eight different catalyzed transformations as well reaction cascades in the presence of natural enzymes.¹⁻⁴

More recently, we have been investigating the potential of artificial metalloenzymes for in vivo catalysis to complement metabolic pathways. In this context, E coli's periplasm has proven particularly versatile.

Reactions implemented thus far:
Hydrogenation (up to 96 % ee)
Transfer Hydrogenation of
 ketones (up to 98 % ee)
 imines (up to 96 % ee)
 enones (up to 1000 TONs)
Allylic Alkylation (up to 95% ee)
C-H Activation (up to 86 % ee)
Olefin Metathesis (up to 140 TONs)
Alcohol Oxidation (up to 250 TONs)
Sulfoxidation (up to 93 % ee)
Dihydroxylation (up to 98 % ee)
NAD⁺ regeneration (up to 20'000 TONs)

Figure. Artificial metalloenzymes obtained upon supramolecular incorporation of a biotinylated organometallic catalyst within streptavidin

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Bispidine coordination chemistry: fundamental principles and applications in medicinal chemistry, bioinorganic modeling and oxidation catalysis.

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Bispidine (3,7-diazabicyclo[3.3.1]nonane) ligands are easy to prepare in a broad variety (mono- and dinucleating ligands with 4 to 8 donor groups per metal ion) and, as adamantane derivatives, these ligands are very rigid and highly preorganized. Metal ion selectivities, redox chemistry and electronics of transition metal bispidine complexes will be discussed on the basis of the coordination geometries enforced by the bispidine backbone, and the emerging features of these complexes will be discussed on the basis of specific applications, ranging from oxidation catalysis based on high-valent metal-oxo complexes to PET (positron emission tomography) and multimodal tumor imaging.[1-4]

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Cytochrome *c* and Myoglobin Oligomers Formed by Domain Swapping

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For half a century, it has been known that cytochrome *c* (cyt *c*) forms polymers, but the polymerization mechanism remained unknown. We found that horse cyt *c* forms polymers by successive domain swapping, where the C-terminal helix is displaced from its original position in the monomer and Met–heme coordination is perturbed significantly [1]. Owing to the dissociation of Met80 from the heme iron in horse cyt *c*, cyanide ion bound to the heme iron in the dimer [2], and the peroxidase activity was enhanced by the dimerization [3]. Domain-swapped oligomeric cyt *c* was produced during refolding from the guanidinium ion-induced unfolded state at high protein concentration and low temperature [4]. It was also produced by refolding from the acid molten globule state to neutral pH state at high protein and ion concentrations [5]. Domain-swapped oligomeric cyt *c* interacted more strongly with anionic phospholipid-containing vesicles and the outer membrane of the HeLa cell, compared to the monomer [6]. Oligomeric cyt *c* induced a lateral phase separation of lipids in the vesicles, leading to membrane disruption.

Pseudomonas aeruginosa cytochrome *c*₅₅₁ (PA cyt *c*₅₅₁), *Hydrogenobacter thermophilus* cytochrome *c*₅₅₂ (HT cyt *c*₅₅₂), and hyperthermophilic bacterium *Aquifex aeolicus* cytochrome *c*₅₅₅ (AA cyt *c*₅₅₅) belong to the cyt *c* protein family. These proteins all formed oligomers, but their swapping regions were different from that of horse cyt *c*. Dimeric PA cyt *c*₅₅₁ and HT cyt *c*₅₅₂ exhibited domain-swapped structures, where the N-terminal α -helix together with the heme was exchanged between protomers [7,8]. Since a relatively strong H-bond network was formed at the loop around the heme-coordinating Met, the C-terminal α -helix did not dissociate from the rest of the protein in dimeric HT cyt *c*₅₅₂ [8]. AA cyt *c*₅₅₅ possesses a unique long 3_{10} - α - 3_{10} helix containing the heme-ligating Met61, and formed dimers by swapping the region containing the extra 3_{10} - α - 3_{10} and C-terminal helices [9]. The unstable loop region may have a tendency to become a hinge loop in domain-swapped proteins, since the hinge loop of domain swapping for cyt *c* family proteins corresponded to the unstable region specified by hydrogen exchange NMR measurements for the monomer, although the swapping region differed among proteins [7].

We also found that myoglobin (Mb) forms a domain-swapped dimer with two extended α -helices [10]. Each new long α -helix was formed by the E and F helices and the EF-loop of the original monomer, and as a result the proximal and distal histidines of the heme originated from different protomers. Although the active site structure of monomeric and dimeric CO-bound Mb was very similar according to FT-IR and Raman measurements, the CO rebinding rate constant (k_{on}) of the dimer was twice larger than that of the monomer [11]. The increase in the size of the channel between a Xe-binding cavity and the solvent by the dimerization may have allowed CO to migrate faster from the solvent, and thus increase the k_{on} value. We also constructed an artificial heterodimeric protein with two different heme active sites (a bis-histidine-coordinated heme and a H₂O/histidine-coordinated heme) using domain swapping

for Mb [12]. We performed a series of folding simulations of two apo-Mb molecules restrained in a high density condition [13]. Separation between monomer folding and domain swapping of Mb arose at a relatively early stage, where inter-chain contacts between helices AB of one chain and helices GH of another chain tend to result in the domain-swapped dimer. This resembled the mechanism of domain swapping suggested for cyt *c* [4].

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Dual Targeting Pt(IV) Anticancer Agents

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The FDA approved platinum anticancer drugs (cisplatin, carboplatin and oxaliplatin) are all square planar Pt(II) drugs that are believed to trigger apoptosis in cancer cells by binding to two adjacent guanines on the same strand. Two of the major drawbacks of these drugs are the need to administer them intravenously and the resistance that cancer cells acquire to these drugs.

One approach aimed at overcoming these drawbacks is to design novel six coordinate octahedral Pt(IV) complexes that act as inert prodrugs that can be administered orally and will release the square planar cytotoxic Pt(II) moiety inside the cancer cell. The intracellular activation of the drug occurs by reductive elimination that results in the simultaneous release of the original Pt(II) drug and the two axial ligands. Thus, the axial ligands can be used for targeting, adding lipophilicity or for dual targeting if they themselves are enzyme inhibitors or anticancer agents.

We tried to gain some insights into the mechanism of action of several Pt(IV) complexes with 4-phenylbutyrate (PhB) or valproate (VPA) axial ligands that are very potent against various kinds of cancer cell lines. Although designed to enhance DNA platination by inhibiting cellular HDAC activity, once inside the cell PhB or VPA can cause many different cellular effects in addition to some HDAC inhibition. We cannot attribute the enhanced cytotoxicity to specific cellular events. However, we believed that the "dual action" complexes really are "multi-action" prodrugs that once they get into the cells they trigger many different events that together lead to the death of the cancer cells.

INVITED LECTURES

Title: Application of paramagnetic metal complexes to study structures and dynamics of protein complexes in the solid state.

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Solid-state NMR is quickly becoming a powerful approach, complementary to solution NMR, for studying structures and dynamics of protein complexes [1-4]. The absence of isotropic tumbling in the solid state removes the intrinsic size limitation, enabling experiments on even very large biomolecular complexes. However, to fully realize this potential further methodological developments are necessary to maximize the sensitivity and spectral resolution and enable site-specific quantitative applications.

In this presentation we discuss a few recent developments in methodology and applications of paramagnetic metal complexes to study structures and dynamics of large protein complexes. We focus on applications involving fast magic angle spinning in the range from 60 to 100 kHz that enable quantitative studies on >300 kDa protein complexes involving a few nanomole quantities of monomer domains.

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Short His-Containing Peptides: Versatile Tools to Design Similar Copper(II) Complexes with Different Properties and Redox Behaviors

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Designing small peptides capable of binding Cu(II) mainly by the side chain functionalities and forming single species in the neutral pH range is a hard task since the amide nitrogens strongly compete for Cu(II) coordination [1]. However, metalloproteins are proficient on this and generate the appropriated coordination pocket to avoid amide coordination. This exquisite control allows copper proteins to attain a myriad of catalytic activities and thus, a large variety of biological functions [2]. Achieving this with short peptides will be very appealing to engineer miniaturized copper proteins with potential redox and hydrolytic activities.

In this communication we report the design and synthesis of a family of decapeptides containing several His but backbones with different degrees of conformational constrain. Their copper(II) coordination properties were studied using pH potentiometry and different spectroscopic methods (UV-Vis, CD, EPR and NMR) [3]. The results show the formation of a similar major copper(II) species at close to neutral pH value where copper(II) is coordinated to the same set of amino acids (3 His and 1 Asp). Nonetheless, due to the distinct flexible nature of their scaffolds different stability constants, as well as copper(II) exchange rates and redox potentials were observed. The implications of these findings in catalysis will be discussed.

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The hemoglobin fragment AGHLDDLPGALSAL: complex-formation properties and biological activity

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Several lines of evidence have shown that limited degradation of certain proteins often leads to the release of endogenous bioactive peptides. Some of them, as hemorphins and hemopressins, are examples of intracellular peptides with antinociceptive effects. Recent research on mouse brain [1] has identified the peptide AGHLDDLPGALSAL (AGH), as a fragment of the α -chain of hemoglobin, which is formed in the cytosol, possessing the ability of inhibiting the peripheral hyperalgesic inflammatory responses through the indirect activation of the mu-opioid receptors. The sequence AGH is also present in other natural peptides, and can be a good prototype of a new class of bioactive compounds.

The role of AGH as endogenous peptide acting as a non-classical neuropeptide, encouraged us to study its coordination properties towards metal ions, never reported so far. In fact, it is worth noticing that the N-terminal sequence of AGH (as well as of its human homologue, VAHVDDMPNALSAL) corresponds to the well-known ATCUN (Amino Terminal Cu and Ni binding) motif, typical of human albumin and characterized by the presence of a histidyl residue in third position. Since AGH is a natural endogenous peptide, its ability to bind metal ions, in competition with albumin, cannot be neglected and may have a role in determining the biological activity of the peptide itself.

On the basis of the above considerations, the complex-formation equilibria of AGH and some analogues with Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} have been investigated by means of various techniques, including potentiometry and mass spectrometry (for the determination of both the stoichiometry and the stability of the formed complexes), UV-visible absorption and circular dichroism spectrophotometry and electron paramagnetic resonance (for Cu^{2+} complexes), to obtain information on the structure of the complexes in solution. In addition, the results of some *in vitro* tests, performed to check the potential protection ability of AGH against the cell toxicity of Cu(II), are reported.

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NEW LIGANDS FOR “NON-BIOLOGICAL” METAL IONS AND NEW APPLICATIONS FOR METALLOPROTEINS

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De novo designed miniature protein scaffolds, such as the coiled coil, offer exciting opportunities for metal ion coordination.[1] Not surprisingly due to the protein like nature of the scaffold, the large majority of *de novo* metallocoiled coil examples have focussed their efforts on mimicking the active sites of native metalloenzymes. Our approach is to instead to use these artificial proteins as novel ligands for the coordination of xeno metals, with no known biological role, with the view to developing functional systems for valuable applications beyond the scope of nature.

We recently reported the design of the first gadolinium coiled coil, which displayed promise as a potential MRI contrast agent.[2] We have since interrogated the coordination of various lanthanide ions to different coiled coil designs and have for the first time shown that we can selectively bind Ln(III) ions, by discriminating based on size, using different designs. We have recently prepared a single coiled coil capable of binding two different Ln(III) ions selectively to two different sites (see Figure). Ultimately we propose this complex to function as a bimodal imaging agent where one site provides a MRI output and the second emits NIR light. These recent results will be reported.

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Metal Complexes of Large Chiral Macrocycles

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Tuning the structure of macrocyclic ligands in order to tailor their metal binding properties is one of the key aspects of inorganic supramolecular chemistry. For instance, the condensation of 2,6-diformylpyridine or 2,6-diformylphenols with chiral diamines affords a variety of macrocyclic Schiff bases that can be easily reduced to the corresponding macrocyclic amines. Depending on the type of substrate and reaction conditions, 2+2, 3+3 or even 4+4 and 6+6 macrocycles can be obtained from these substrates. These macrocycles can be used to achieve the challenging task of controlled formation of enantiopure complexes, where helical twist of the macrocycle is dictated by the chirality of the diamine fragment. The large size of these ligands allows binding of relatively large metal ions such as lanthanide(III) or lead(II) ions. In addition, the 3+3 macrocyclic amines based on 2,6-diformylphenols are big enough to accommodate three metal ions in the center (Fig. 1), thus forming trinuclear copper(II) complexes [1] or trinuclear lanthanide(III) complexes [2], which exhibit interesting magnetic properties. On the other hand, the corresponding 3+3 Schiff bases form container-like trinuclear zinc(II) complex, where metal ions stitch together two macrocyclic units [3]. In the solid state these complexes form a channel-type structure leading to gas adsorption properties. Moreover, in the case of this system a unique template effect is observed - the size of the formed macrocycle is determined by the amount of the metal template used (Fig. 2) [3]. Even larger complexes are formed by 6+6 meso-type macrocycles that are able to bind six metal ions [4].

The chiral nature of these macrocycles in combination with the coordination requirements of metal ions lead to new interesting phenomena:

- the lanthanide complexes of 2+2 and 3+3 macrocyclic amines exhibit the unique controlled helicity inversion process [5,6]. Controlled chirality switching is a rare process related to various systems such metal complexes, DNA, supramolecular assemblies and as organic polymers.
- the formation of dinuclear hydroxo bridged Ln(III) complexes of the 2+2 Schiff base macrocycle, as well as the formation of chiral metallacavitand based on 3+3 macrocycle and zinc(II) ions are accompanied by the enantiomeric self-recognition of the chiral macrocyclic units.
- the lanthanide(III) complexes of chiral 2+2 Schiff base catalyse the enantioselective cleavage of supercoiled plasmid DNA [7]
- the lanthanide(III) complexes of chiral 3+3 amine show contrasting enantioselective DNA preference [8]

Figure 1. Trinuclear Dy(III) complex of a 3+3 chiral amine.

Figure 2. The influence of the amount of Zn(II) template on the size of the macrocycle formed in the reaction of 1,2-trans-diaminocyclohexane (green) and 4-tert-butyl-2,6-diformylphenol (red).

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Molecular Self-Assembling Mediated by Pyrazole Macrocycles

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1*H*-Pyrazole is an imidazole isomer which has the heterocyclic nitrogen atoms in adjacent positions.¹ Due to this disposition, 1*H*-pyrazole, has a very rich and versatile chemistry based on its capability to behave as a hydrogen bond donor and acceptor or monodentate ligand in neutral form and as hydrogen bond acceptor or bis(monodentate) ligand in its pyrazolate anionic form. Even though these characteristics have been widely explored for the construction of more or less sophisticated molecular ensembles, the inclusion of 1*H*-pyrazole moieties as a part of mono- or polycyclic structures is not so well-known.^{2,3} In this talk we will discuss this point and we will show as azamacrocycles with 1*H*-pyrazole spacers have an amazing structural diversity which facilitates their specific interaction with substrates of biological or environmental relevance.

Figura 1. Metalocajas de pirazol

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Platinum binding to RNA: interaction of oxaliplatin with an RNA internal loop

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Studying the interaction of platinum drugs with molecular targets other than DNA is important for a more comprehensive understanding of their activity. Among others, RNA is an attractive potential target. It was shown that cisplatin can inhibit RNA-related processes, and platinum-RNA interactions were recently confirmed in spectroscopic and biochemical studies [1-3]. Though, little is known on RNA structural changes upon platinum binding.

In this context, we are currently investigating the interaction of oxaliplatin with a short RNA construct containing a classic internal loop, with stacked adenines and a uracil mismatch [4], aiming at elucidating the effect of these structural motifs on metal complex binding. The interaction was initially studied using gel mobility shift assays, and the conditions for obtaining and isolating monoplatinated samples were optimized. The pure monoplatinated samples are currently being characterized using a combination of techniques, including, e.g., UV-Vis melting temperature studies, partial alkaline hydrolysis and enzymatic digestion of ³²P 5'- and 3'-end labelled samples. Moreover, time evolution NMR experiments were performed to identify preferential binding sites. For these latter studies, two additional constructs were used, one missing the internal loop and the second having a different terminal loop, to evaluate the effect of these isolated structural elements on platinum interaction. Interestingly, our preliminary results suggest that small structure modifications can strongly influence the binding.

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Vanadium metallodrugs in cancer therapeutics. A molecular approach.

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The omnipresence of vanadium in biological systems stands out as a distinct paradigm of an inorganic cofactor influencing cellular processes key to the physiology of organisms [1]. Its presence in metalloenzyme systems such as nitrogenases and haloperoxidases attests to the essential interjection of that element in serving catalytic functions at the cellular level. Concurrently, the effects of vanadium as an exogenous inorganic cofactor in enzyme systems overtly suggest that its chemistry at the biological level offers opportunities in its exploitation in a number of aberrant processes, including diseases. In this regard, the insulin mimetic activity and anticarcinogenic activity of vanadium constitute clear examples of how that element could help remedy cellular dysfunctions and rectify cellular physiology [2,3]. Poised to explore the chemistry of vanadium in cellular processes linked to carcinogenesis, research efforts were launched in our lab to a) design, synthesize and physicochemically characterize well-defined forms of vanadium metallodrugs capable of antitumorogenic activity, b) investigate the biology of selected vanadium species with respect to tumor suppressing properties and signaling pathways associated with cancer cytoplasmic and nuclear processes [4,5]. To this end, a) synthetic approaches based on the physiologically relevant oxidation states V(IV) and V(V) were employed with physiological substrates and hydrogen peroxide, ultimately leading to ternary V(V)-H₂O₂-amino acid/betaine species, isolated and fully characterized in the solid state and in solution. The employment of such vanadoforms in cancer cell lines revealed the concentration-dependent effect that vanadium exerts on the selective demise of aberrant cells compared to physiological non-cancerous cells. The influence of vanadium covers key signaling oncogenes, such as H-ras, enzymes such MMP-2, and directs cells to apoptotic death through ROS-dependent activity. Processes such as autophagy, TRAIL-induced apoptosis and miRNA intervention attest to the potential of that element in inflicting selective damage and thus cell death through actions linked to both cytoplasmic and nuclear processes [6,7]. Collectively, the bioinorganic chemistry and biology of the adopted approach converge into a multidisciplinary strategy, providing the key to unlock the complex behavior of vanadium in cancer physiology, thereby laying out the ground work for the development of effective molecular vanadodrug biotechnology in cancer therapeutics.

Figure 1: Three dimensional presentation of the anion in a ternary V(V)-peroxido-betaine species

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Towards understanding the folding dynamics of the G-quadruplex sequence at the 5'-UTR of the human BCL2 mRNA

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G-quadruplexes (G4) are non-canonical secondary structures of nucleic acids present in guanine rich DNA and RNA sequences. In the presence of metal ions, these sequences fold into stable tetra-helical structures formed by the coplanar cyclic arrangement of four Hoogsteen-paired guanines. The resulting guanine tetrads stack on top to each other building the final G4 structure (Fig. 1) [1]. Potassium(I) has proven to be the most stabilizing metal ion. Interestingly, K^+ is also the monovalent cation with the highest intracellular concentration. The high prevalence of G4-forming sequences in the human genome strongly indicates a selective pressure to maintain these sequences on the genome, supporting a regulatory function of G4 *in vivo*.

Fig. 1. A) G-tetrad structure showing four Gs linked via H-bonds. A metal ion is in the centre of the structure. B) Schematic view of a parallel-folded G4 structure.

The BCL2 (B-cell Lymphoma/leukemia 2) proto-oncogene encodes for the BCL2 family of proteins which play a crucial role in the regulation of apoptosis [2]. The regulation of this gene occurs both at the transcriptional and posttranscriptional level. The formation *in cellulo* of a G-quadruplex structure in the 5'-UTR mRNA of the BCL2 proto-oncogene has proven to down-regulate its protein expression [3]. Therefore, the understanding of this biologically relevant RNA G4 sequence is of high interest for anticancer therapy.

In the context of the native 5'-UTR, we synthesized the 25-mer G4-forming sequence (5'-G₅CCGUG₄UG₃AGCUG₄-3') and investigated its folding in the presence of K(I) ions. 1D ¹H-NMR spectra revealed the formation of multiple G4 structures in this mRNA. This is because the sequence contains 18 Gs from which only 12 can be actually involved in the G-quadruplex formation. Thus, different polymorphs can be folded by shifting single nucleotides in the structure. To further investigate the folding of this human G-quadruplex-forming sequence and reduce the dynamics of the system at the same time, two Gs at the 5'- and one at the 3'-end were deleted leading to a more restricted 22-mer BCL2 G4-forming sequence (5'-G₃CCGUG₄UG₃AGCUG₃-3'). Data obtained from the UV/Vis, CD and EMSA characterization of this sequence showed the stabilization of mainly one G4 structure upon the addition of K^+ , which can be defined as unimolecular, intramolecular and parallel-stranded.

Preliminary structural data obtained by NMR suggest the presence of two different but non-equally populated species in solution that involve all the Gs within the central G₄-track (Fig 2). To date, single mutation of the guanines present in the central track seems to promote the guanine bases located in the loops to participate in new G₄ conformations in which the formation of bulges is requested (Fig. 2).

A) 22-mer BCL2 5'- G G G C C G U G G G G U G G G A G C U G G G -3'
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 21 22

B)

Fig. 2. (A) 22-mer BCL2 RNA G₄-forming sequence with numbering. A, G, C, U corresponds to adenine, guanine, cytosine and uracil nucleobases. Gs in the tracks are underlined. (B) Scheme of the different folding possibilities in the 22-mer BCL2 G₄ sequence. Those Gs involved in the G-tetrads or in the loops are coloured in white or yellow, respectively. G8 and G11 (in the central G₄-track) are framed in red. G6 and G17 (in the loops) are framed in green when involved in the G-tetrads. Only one nucleotide bulge is considered. G₄ folding with two-nucleotide bulges is also possible.

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Impact of Metal Complexes on the Binding and Activation of G-Protein Coupled Receptor Binding Peptides

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Our group uses the unique spectroscopic and chemical properties of organometallic complexes in metal-peptide conjugates for biomedical applications. The experimental challenge is to identify air- and water stable organometallic compounds with the desired properties, and to devise methods for the mild, biocompatible synthesis of bioconjugates with these metal complexes. For a long time, we have been working on derivatives of the neuropeptide Enkephalin (Enk).^[1, 2] Enkephalin is a five amino acid peptide with the primary sequence H-Tyr-Gly-Gly-Phe-Leu(or Met)-OH. It binds to the opioid receptors in the central nervous system, which belong to the now-famous class of G-protein coupled receptors (GPCRs). Enk itself has little preference for either of the three sub-classes (μ , δ , or κ) of this receptor.

This lecture presents the solid phase synthesis of metal-peptide conjugates for targeting such GPCRs. The first solution structure by NMR of a Cp^{*}Rh complex covalently linked to the cyclic peptide somatostatin was recently solved by us.^[3] Subsequently, the solution structure of the much more flexible Cp^{*}Rh-Enk derivatives was also established, and the binding to the opioid receptors was investigated by molecular modelling. Interestingly, two different binding modes were discovered for the naturally occurring Enk peptide, but only one of those was feasible for the metal-Enk derivative.^[4] Most recently, our group prepared the first metal derivatives of the peptide dermorphin, which unlike Enk has some specificity for the μ opioid receptor. By placing a bulky Re(CO)₃ derivative at various different positions within the peptide sequence, the metal complex could serve as a molecular lock, and thereby force the binding of the peptide into hitherto unknown different modes. These different binding modes were further characterized by molecular modelling, and the physiological consequences were investigated experimentally.

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Solid phase equilibria: our story, past, present and future.

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From balloons (on the left, Chelex 100 seeds at microscope) to flowers (on the right, film membranes differently coloured depending on metal ion and/or its concentration)

Our research has been and still is based on the study of different solid phases that exhibit chelating, or simply exchange properties, towards metal ions. Characterisation of sorption reactions, elucidation of mechanism, modelling of these reactions, and more recently development of new solid materials have been the driving force of our work.

Initially, our investigation was based on commercial resins, such as carboxylic and iminodiacetic solids, i.d. Chelex 100 and Amberlite CG-50. Actually, the model adopted to describe the sorption of metal ions on these materials was developed some years before, studying anionic resins in which the active group, a negatively charged azo dye was sorbed by ion exchange. This experimental arrangement – strong anionic resin-sulphonic azodyes-proton and metal ions – offered a simplified system to develop a model for bi-phasic data treatment, since the properties of ligands were well known, the concentration of the ionic media in the resin phase constant [1]. The model was based on the existence of Donnan potential at the interface resin/solution. Accordingly, the resin phase works as a concentrated water solution, with the same standard and reference states, and the distribution coefficient of a metal ion, which depends on the experiment set up, can be calculated on the base of universal properties, which do not depend on experimental conditions. Many efforts have been devoted to the characterisation of the sorption mechanism of many metal ions, defining the exchange reactions and their intrinsic complexation constants [2].

The development of the model and the use of resins to preconcentrate environmental water samples for metal ions determination was indeed the main topic of our research in the following decade. The main consequence of these studies was the development of the “resin titration” method: treating a natural water sample with different amount of solid phase, it is possible to establish the total metal concentration and have information on the metal species in the original sample. Speciation of a metal ion is of paramount importance for its fate in the environment. We almost always found that in natural samples the amount of free metal is really negligible, especially when the metal ion is present at sub-trace level, and that very strong and dilute ligands must be responsible of metal complexation [3].

The method was applied on environmental samples of pristine waters such as Antarctic sea and lake waters, Mediterranean sea waters, estuarine, river, thermal and spring waters.

The method was applied also on beverages, such as grape wines, teas, always with the intent to determine the total metal content and to evaluate the metal speciation [4]. The accuracy of the method was tested through inter-comparison trials.

In the following years, our interest moved towards new solid phase specifically designed, and the core example still is the immobilisation of DFO on silica gel and the application to urine samples for quantification of Fe(III) and the evaluation of its speciation. [5-6] The same ligand was successfully immobilized also on filtering paper.

More recently, an azacryptand containing two tripodal tetra-amine receptor was fixed on silica MCM41 and Amberlite CG-50 supports for separation and extraction of perhenate and pertechnetate from water solution. The solid phase showed promising properties, not only as sensors for these anionic radionuclides, but also in batch and fixed bed column system separation of TcO_4^- from MoO_4^{2-} [7], so that currently a feasibility study for a radio-medical application is taking place.

In a recent collaboration with José Miguel García, we designed a methacrylate membrane which includes kojic acid, previously transformed into an acrylic monomer, further copolymerized with hydrophilic co-monomers to render a membrane comprised of a hydrophilic, gel-like, polymer network. The film-like membrane was used in small sensory discs or squares for iron(III) sensing and quantification.

Lately, two well known metal ions indicators, i.e. Dithizone and Alizarin Red S, were tested for sensors in optode membranes of divalent and trivalent cations simultaneous determination. More details can be found in the poster section. The resulting transparent triacetylcellulose membranes change their colour, depending on the metal ion, and/or the mixture of metal ions present in solution in contact with them, while the quantification of different ions will be obtained through multivariate data analysis.

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Structural, electronic, magnetic and biological properties of coordination compounds with azole derivatives

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Mono- bis- and tris-azole heterocyclics play important biological roles; as these polyfunctional molecules bear nitrogen, oxygen and sulfur atoms as basic sites for coordination and acidic protons, which can be substituted by Lewis acids [1,2]. These ligands may give place to a variety of metal-ligand coordination modes. They may favour the formation of six membered rings, by inclusion of a metal ion in a planar delocalized system, and promote intra and inter-molecular interactions, such as hydrogen bonding and π - stacking, yielding supramolecular aggregates. Our aim was to study the effect of heteroatoms (nitrogen, oxygen or sulfur) in these aromatic N-donor molecules upon coordination towards Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} , and their effect on their chemical, electronic, magnetic and structural behavior. The structural characterization, as electronic and magnetic properties of a series of azole derivatives of mono and polynuclear coordination compounds will be discussed, as well as the biological activity of some of the studied compounds.

$[(\text{Ni}(\text{bztb})_2 \cdots (\text{H}_2\text{O})_3 \cdots \text{Ni}(\text{bztb})_2)]$

$[\text{Cu}(\text{tnz})_2\text{Cl}_2]$

Thermodynamic and kinetic conformers

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The copper and zinc chelation properties of metformin and representative sartan molecules.

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Heart disease is the major cause of death in diabetes, a disorder characterized by chronic hyperglycemia and cardiovascular complications. Altered systemic regulation of transition metals in diabetes has been the subject of previous investigation, but it has not been ascertained whether changed transition metal metabolism results in heart disease in common forms of diabetes and whether metal chelation can reverse the condition [1].

Copper is an essential but highly toxic metal that is strictly regulated in biological systems. In diabetes, the impaired copper regulation manifests as elevations in urinary Cu^{II} excretion, systemic chelatable-Cu^{II} and full copper balance, in increased pro-oxidant stress and defective antioxidant defenses, and in the progressive damage to the blood vessels, heart, kidneys, retina and nerves [2]. Zinc is required for normal immune function and taste acuity and enhances the in vitro effectiveness of insulin. Impaired immune function and taste have been reported in diabetic subjects, and decreased serum zinc levels and hyperzincuria occur in diabetic patients and animals [3].

Several different classes of drugs are currently in use by diabetic patients. In particular, metformin is widely used and has multiple beneficial impacts on patients with type 2 diabetes. It can effectively lower HbA_{1c} values, positively affects lipid profiles, and improves vascular and hemodynamic indices [4]. Age-associated increases in collagen cross-linking and accumulation of advanced glycosylation products are both accelerated by diabetes, suggesting that glucose-derived cross-link formation may contribute to the development of chronic diabetic complications as well as certain physical changes of aging. Aminoguanidine prevented both the formation of advanced non-enzymatic glycation products and the formation of glucose-derived collagen cross-links in vitro[5]. The pyridoxal-

aminoguanidine adduct with both anti-glycation and antioxidant activities protects streptozotocin-diabetic rats against neuropathy and cataract [6]. Sartans are an important class of drugs whose principal action is as selective antagonists of angiotensin II and AT1 receptors. They are commonly used to treat hypertension, and have further therapeutic indications include the management of congestive heart failure, myocardial infarction, and diabetic nephropathy [7].

Here we hypothesized that, based on their structures, metformin and sartans could act as transition metal chelators. We have therefore studied the ability of metformin and two representative sartan molecules to bind Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions. We now report that all three drug molecules exhibit binding properties consistent with actions as effective ligands for Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions, pointing to a potential new mechanism of action of these compounds. The possible significance of these findings is discussed.

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Metal ion complexes of some tren- and tach-based tripodal ligands

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In order to create highly efficient low molecular weight enzyme mimics, recently we synthesized several new tris(2-aminoethyl)amin (tren) and cis,cis-1,3,5-triaminocyclohexane (tach) based tripodal ligands (Figure 1) possessing quite different coordination properties.

From the enzyme mimetic point of view, the tripodal ligands have several advantages over the linear and even macrocyclic ligands. These ligands have enhanced chelate effect, and preorganized structure (reduced number of relevant binding conformations) resulting higher stability of the complexes. Tripodal ligands enforce ‘facial’ metal binding and (partly) enclose the metal ion, similarly to metalloenzymes. By adequate substitution of the tripodal platform it is possible to fine tune the metal binding ability, and allow creating additional functionalities, such as substrate binding and/or substrate activation. Substituents may also directly influence the steric

environment around the metal centre or may provide additional metal binding site, inducing metal-metal cooperation during the catalytic cycle.

Since the pyridine nitrogens in **L**¹ and **L**² are not able to coordinate the metal ion bound to the tripodal units, the ML complexes formed in the neutral pH range have trigonal bipyramidal (**L**¹) and square pyramidal geometry (**L**²), similarly to the tren or tach complexes. At higher pH mixed hydroxo complexes are formed. The presence of pyridine rings in **L**² hinder the formation of the dihydroxo bridged dinuclear complex observed in the Cu(II)-tach system. The species Cu**L**²(OH) is an active catalyst for the hydrolysis of phosphodiester.

Although **L**⁴ forms stable 5/6N coordinated ML⁴ complexes with Cu(II) and Zn(II), the trigonal bipyramidal binding site of **L**³ has higher metal ion affinity, including Mn(II) and Fe(II). In the cases of both ligands, the pyrrole nitrogens of the Cu(II)-bound pyrazole rings create a further metal binding site via pyrazolato bridges, and thus tricopper complexes are formed. The appearance of Cu₃H₄L₂ species even in equimolar solution is noteworthy,

Figure 1.

especially considering that its formation results in the liberation of a bound ligand $3\text{CuL} = \text{Cu}_3\text{H}_4\text{L}_2 + \text{L} + 4\text{H}^+$, despite the high stability of CuL . Therefore, the formation of the trinuclear complexes is thermodynamically highly preferred, and can be regarded as a pH-driven spontaneous self-assembly. In the crystal structure of $[\text{Cu}_3\text{H}_4(\text{L}^4)_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \times 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ the two outer copper(II) are 5N coordinated in square pyramidal geometry, while the central copper(II) is bound to four deprotonated pyrrolic nitrogens in tetrahedral geometry. The tricopper complexes of both ligands are highly active catecholase mimics working at surprisingly low pH (5-7). Since the mononuclear $\text{CuL}^{3/4}$ species do not show catecholase activity, we assume that the central tetrahedral copper(II) ion has fundamental role in the catechol binding.

The presence of C- and N-terminal histidines in the two tripodal peptide derivatives (L^5 and L^6 , respectively) results in basically different structures. Between pH 4-10, the mononuclear Cu(II) complexes of L^5 have identical Gly-His-like $\{\text{N}_{\text{imi}}, \text{N}_{\text{amid}}^-, \text{N}_{\text{tert}}\}$ coordination mode, indicating its outstanding stability. Above pH 9, the copper promoted deprotonation of a second amide nitrogen induces trigonal bipyramidal distortion. The remaining two ‘legs’ of L^5 are able to coordinate a second metal ion. At $\text{Cu(II)/L}^5 = 2/1$ ratio the formation of dinuclear complexes starts at pH 3-4, and the $\{\text{N}_{\text{imi}}, \text{N}_{\text{amid}}^-, \text{N}_{\text{tert}} + 2\text{COO}^-, \text{N}_{\text{imi}}\}$ binding mode of Cu_2L^5 changes successively to $\{\text{N}_{\text{imi}}, \text{N}_{\text{amid}}^-, \text{N}_{\text{tert}} + 2\text{N}_{\text{imi}}, 2\text{N}_{\text{amid}}^-\}$ up to pH 10. In the Cu(II)- and Zn(II)- L^6 systems the *bis*-histamine-like coordinated ML^6 or M_3L^6_2 complexes are formed at neutral pH depending on the metal-to-ligand ratio. The loosely (if any) bound third ‘leg’ of two ML^6 complexes create a third metal binding site in M_3L^6_2 . At higher pH amide coordinated complexes are formed. Above pH 7, the oligonuclear complexes of both L^5 and L^6 have efficient catecholase activity.

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Speciation and structure of the Ni(II)/nitrate system in BumimTf₂N Ionic Liquid

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Room temperature Ionic Liquids (RTILs) have recently attracted much attention as environmental friendly solvents owing to their practically negligible vapor pressure, stability and low toxicity. RTILs are composed of an anionic and a cationic part that both strongly influence their physicochemical properties such as density, viscosity, phase transitions, miscibility with water and other solvents and electrochemical properties. All these liquid properties can be finely tuned by changing the cation/anion pair to give a RTIL optimized for a given application.

These features make RTILs promising alternative solvents with respect to conventional volatile organic ones, especially for separation and extraction processes [1]. Many works focused on the application of RTILs in a variety of separation processes for chemical analysis and to recover metal cations which can be toxic for the environment and living organisms [1, 2]. Moreover, RTILs emerged as interesting media for nuclear fuel reprocessing, in replacement of volatile organic solvents for liquid-liquid partitioning of actinides and lanthanides [3].

Despite the general interest on RTILs for separations of transition metals still a lot remains to be known about the cation solvation structure and the complex formation in these media.

In this work we present early results of the experimental and theoretical study of Ni²⁺ solvation and complex formation with nitrate ions in the “classical” RTIL 1-methyl-3 butylimidazolium bistriflimide (BumimTf₂N). The choice of nitrate ligand as complexant is due to the fact that liquid-liquid extraction experiments are often carried out with aqueous solutions containing high nitrate concentration. The Ni²⁺ cation does not form stable species with nitrate in aqueous solution, while in weakly coordinating aprotic molecular solvents, such as acetonitrile, stable complexes were observed [4]. This suggests that the Ni²⁺ cation may be present as mixture of nitrate species in the extracted RTIL sample.

Spectroscopic and molecular dynamics (MD) studies have been carried out to obtain complementary structural information on the species in solution. The MD force field definitions for BumimTf₂N and parameters for Ni(II) and nitrate were taken from ref. [5].

EXAFS spectra and Molecular Dynamics simulations confirm that Ni²⁺ ion is 6-coordinated in anhydrous BumimTf₂N by the oxygen atoms of the Tf₂N anion, which can be either mono- or bidentate (Figure 1). When nitrate is added, EXAFS spectra show that up to three species are formed. In addition it is evidenced that nitrate behaves always as bidentate ligand.

Figure 1. Snapshot of the MD simulation of Ni(II) in BumimTf₂N RTIL.

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ORAL COMUNICATIONS

Poly-His protein fragments from snake venoms as unusual domains in metal ion binding

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Snake venoms are complex mixtures of proteins, nucleotides and inorganic ions. These combinations confer a formidable array of toxic properties on the venom. However, snake venom is also a natural biological resource of several components with huge therapeutic potential [1].

The novel families of natural peptides that have been found in the African viper, *Atheris squamigera*, are poly-His-poly-Gly peptides and have the sequence EDDHHHHHHHHG (pHpG-1). These peptides consist of nine consecutive His residues and ten consecutive Gly residues. It has been proposed that these families of pHpG-1 peptides may protect against snake venom – inhibiting proteolysis by some of the proteins of the snake venom [2, 3]. The most interesting in this sequence is polyhistidine peptide fragment.

The specific role of the polyhistidine fragments (His-tag) is unknown, but we know, that domains with His-tag motif are very often found in nature [4] and commonly used for purification of recombinant proteins in IMAC chromatography [5].

In order to determine the thermodynamic properties, stoichiometry, binding sites and structures of the metal-EDDHHHHHHHHHG complexes we used a combination of experimental techniques and extensive computational tools. The results showed that pHG has a high affinity towards metal ions. The numerous histidine residues located along this sequence are efficient metal ion chelators, with high affinity towards Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions. The formation of an α -helical structure induced by metal ion coordination and the occurrence of polymorphic binding states is very specific for polyhistidine tag domains [6, 7].

It is proposed that metal ions can ‘move along’ the poly-His tag, which serves as a metal ion transport pathway. The coordination of Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Zn²⁺ ions to the polyhistidine fragments is very effective in comparison to other histidine-rich peptides.

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Visualization of Intracellular Metals by Scanning X-ray Fluorescence Microscopy- Application for Cell Biology and Medicine

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Elements (i.e., minerals and metals) are essential for a healthy body. On the other hand, the intracellular distribution of elements and its function are not well understood, although studies related to proteins and nucleic acids have been conducted at the molecular level. We have developed a scanning X-ray fluorescence microscope system (SXF) that can reliably determine the cellular distribution of multiple elements with high spatial resolution [1-5]. Visualizing intracellular elements and understanding their kinetics may provide great insight into the behaviors of elements at the molecular level in biology and medicine. In this study, we introduce applications to artificial nickel-ion trafficking complexes and cellular response against platinum anti-cancer drug using an element array by SXFM, which shows a profile of multiple elements at single-cell level [3-5].

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Contribution of Thiazolyle Arms in the Stability of Cu(II)/Cu(I) Polyazacycloalcanes-based Chelates for PET Imaging

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Positron Emission Tomography (PET) is a non invasive molecular imaging mode in great development for tumoral diseases diagnostic and radiotherapy control. The principle is based on the introduction of a β^+ emitter radionuclide which reaches the targeting area to visualise *via* a biological vector. Clinical examination currently use the radiopharmaceutical ^{18}F -FDG ($[^{18}\text{F}]$ -fluorodeoxyglucose) in which the radionuclide ^{18}F is covalently linked to the biomolecule. β^+ emitter cationic radiometallic elements with interesting half-time life in a biological point of view, as $^{64}\text{Cu}^{2+}$ ($t_{1/2}$ 12,7 h), are involved in numerous research works in the aim to elaborate chelates offering ideal radiopharmaceutical features as a fast complexation, a good thermodynamic stability and a kinetic inertness. Another important factor to consider in future radiopharmaceuticals synthesis is the stability of the chelate face to potential reductors in biological media which can induce the decomplexation of the chelator after reduction of the radionuclide $^{64}\text{Cu(II)}$ into $^{64}\text{Cu(I)}$ and can give rise to transchelation [1,2].

Our group develops the synthesis of new chelates based on tri- and tetra-azamacrocycles with interesting physico-chemical properties for radiopharmaceutical applications in imaging and therapy [3,4, 5]. New derivatives of cyclam (**te1th** and **te2th**) and tacn (**no2th**), functionalised by potential ambident thiazolyle arms, have been synthesised and their Cu(II) complexation studied. Synthesis and results concerning the complex properties in solid state and in solution will be presented. The ability of these new chelators to stabilise Cu(I) oxidation state will also be discussed.

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Metal Ion-Binding Properties of the Monoprotonated Phosphonate Residue of 9-[2-(Phosphonomethoxy)ethyl]-2-amino-6-dimethylaminopurine (PME2A6DMAP).

A Model for the Metal Ion Affinity of Phosphoryl-Diester Bridges

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Substituents at a purine residue can strongly affect its metal ion-binding properties [1]. Indeed, the various substituents in PME2A6DMAP^{2-} prevent any remarkable M^{2+} interaction with any of the N sites in $\text{M}(\text{PME2A6DMAP})$ complexes [2]. Is the analogous observation also valid for the monoprotonated $\text{M}(\text{H};\text{PME2A6DMAP}^+)$ complexes? Before dealing with

this question, it is helpful to consider the situation in the complexes of $\text{H}(\text{PME2AP})^-$ [3], where $\text{PME2AP} = 9\text{-[2-(phosphonomethoxy)ethyl]-2-aminopurine}$, which is a close relative of the antivirally active, acyclic nucleotide analogue 9-[2-(phosphonomethoxy)ethyl]adenine (PMEA) [4, 5]. In the case of PME2AP the N1 and N3 sites are equally screened by the (C2)NH₂ substituent, but N7 is freely accessible [1, 3]. Indeed, for the complexes of Mn^{2+} ,

M^{2+}	$\log K_{\text{M}(\text{H};\text{PE})}^{\text{M}}$ for the complexes	
	$\text{M}(\text{H};\text{PME2AP})^+$	$\text{M}(\text{H};\text{PME2A6DMAP})^+$
Mg^{2+}	0.82 ± 0.10	0.49 ± 0.17
Ca^{2+}	0.7 ± 0.2	0.45 ± 0.17
Mn^{2+}	0.93 ± 0.14	0.91 ± 0.17
Ni^{2+}	2.05 ± 0.09	0.88 ± 0.12
Cu^{2+}	2.77 ± 0.07	1.61 ± 0.19
Zn^{2+}	1.77 ± 0.09	1.03 ± 0.21

Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , and Zn^{2+} the stability constants of the $\text{M}(\text{H};\text{PME2AP})^+$ complexes follow the Irving-Williams series (see also the Table, where $\text{PE}^{2-} = \text{PME2AP}^{2-}$ or PME2A6DMAP^{2-}), indicating N7 innersphere binding [3] [the analogous observation, though less pronounced, is made for the related $\text{M}(\text{H};\text{PMEA})^+$ complexes]. Furthermore, the same stability enhancements were observed for all

five $\text{M}(\text{H};\text{PME2AP})^+$ complexes and this is attributed to outersphere macrochelate formation with the monoprotonated $\text{P}(\text{O})_2^-(\text{OH})$ residue, the formation degree being $64 \pm 13\%$. A comparison of the acidity constants shows [2] that in the $\text{M}(\text{H};\text{PME2A6DMAP})^+$ complexes the proton is at the phosphonate group. Where are the metal ions located? In the context of this question it is revealing to compare the stability constants listed in the Table: Evidently the stabilities of the $\text{M}(\text{H};\text{PME2A6DMAP})^+$ complexes are smaller than those of the $\text{M}(\text{H};\text{PME2AP})^+$ species, despite the increased basicity of about 1 pK unit of the

2-amino-6-dimethylaminopurine residue [2, 3]. Moreover, the order of the stability values corresponds typically to the one observed for phosph(on)ate binding [6, 7]. Further comparisons confirm the conclusion that in the $M(H;PME2A6DMAP)^+$ complexes both, the proton and the metal ions, are located at the phosph(on)ate residue. In nucleic acids metal ions bind to the phosphoryl-diester bridges, $RO-P(O)_2^-(OR')$, via the $P(O)_2^-$ unit. The same unit is part of the $P(O)_2^-(OH)$ group of the $M(H;PME2A6DMAP)^+$ complexes. Therefore, the stability data for the latter complexes are also excellent mimics of the metal ion affinity of the $P(O)_2^-$ unit in phosphoryl-diester bridges. Hence, the data listed in the Table provide the first comprehensive set [2] of this urgently needed type of stability data. In agreement with earlier conclusions binding occurs mainly in an outersphere manner.

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Thermodynamic, Kinetic and Structural Study of Transition Metal Complexes of NOTA ligand

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Triaza-macrocyclic ligands are recently utilized to bind some radioisotopes for application in medicinal chemistry (^{60–64,67}Cu, ^{66–68}Ga, ^{86,90}Y, ¹¹¹In) [1,2]. Among them, copper radioisotopes are promising for application in diagnosis (positron emission tomography - PET, ⁶⁴Cu with half-life 12.8 h) or in radio-immunotherapy (⁶⁷Cu with half-life 62 h) [1,2]. Cu(II) ion should be bound in the form of metal complexes of high thermodynamic stability and kinetic inertness, which are required for the use *in vivo* for medical purposes [1–3]. One of the most frequently used triaza-macrocyclic ligand is H₃nota (1,4,7-triazacyclononane-1,4,7-triacetic acid; Scheme). Despite that, broad range of basic data regarding structural and some thermodynamic properties and kinetic behavior of its complexes has not been reported [4].

Scheme: Formula of 1,4,7-triazacyclononane-1,4,7-triacetic acid (H₃nota)

Here, we report on protonation constants as well as stability constants of metal complexes (Cu(II), Zn(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Cd(II), Pb(II), Ca(II), Mg(II)) which show that the ligand cavity is too small for large metal ions and, therefore, the stability constants are significantly decreasing. This observation was confirmed for molecular structure of [Pb(nota)]⁻ complex found in the solid state. The kinetic studies show the fast formation and slow dissociation of copper(II) complexes and, therefore, this ligand is suitable for sequestering of copper radioisotopes utilized in nuclear medicine. The results are compared with rate constants obtained for open-chain ligands, *e.g.* EDTA, or other triazamacrocyclic ligands without pendant arms.

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New thermodynamic and structural insights into plutonium(IV) complexation with open-chain and cyclic polyaminocarboxylic acids

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Our aim is to investigate the coordination chemistry in aqueous media of selected 5f elements with environmentally and technologically-relevant organic chelators. Among them, open-chain but also macrocyclic polyaminocarboxylic acids, also named complexones, have attracted our attention [1]. The archetypal EDTA⁴⁻ and DTPA⁵⁻ are ubiquitous ligands, which have found widespread applications in nuclear sciences and industry as mostly efficient analytical reagents, metal-ion scavengers, extractants for reprocessing spent nuclear fuels, or in-vivo decorporating agents. As a consequence, these aminocarboxylic acids and their salts are also present in large amounts in nuclear wastes. For example, about 80 tons of EDTA are contained in the highly radioactive liquid wastes stored on the US Hanford site, which were generated by the manufacturing of nuclear weapons. Leakages of the storage tanks have resulted in the release of an estimated amount of 4 000 m³ of liquids into the ground, representing a total activity of more than one million Curies. Owing to its high acidity and thus propensity to hydrolyse even at pH values below 1, tetravalent plutonium is mainly found in the environment in the form of small oligomeric clusters or colloids which can attach themselves to natural minerals or organic colloids. Most importantly, several investigations have underlined the mobility enhancement of colloidal plutonium in contaminated soils and sediments in the presence of complexones like EDTA.

In spite of the technological, environmental, and medicinal significance of such chelators, their coordination chemistry with respect to 5f-elements still remains a matter of debate [2]. As far as plutonium(IV) is concerned, equilibrium studies are scarce and moreover essentially unreliable. Collecting structural and self-consistent thermodynamic data pertaining to the solution species under rigorously controlled experimental conditions is not only intended to fill some gaps in the scientific literature, but is sought also as a mean to predict the behavior of actinides once released into the geo- and biosphere, or to control the partitioning phenomena in industrial separation processes.

The complexation equilibria of plutonium(IV) with EDTA⁴⁻ and DTPA⁴⁻ in nitrate media at 298 K will be discussed in light of potentiometric, spectrophotometric, capillary electrophoretic, and X-ray absorption spectroscopic (XAS) studies. Global modelling enabled to determine the formation constants of several, hitherto unknown, 1:2 species.

Contrasting with the chelation properties of their linear counterparts, tetraazamacrocyclic *N,N',N'',N'''*-tetracarboxylic acids readily form highly-insoluble

plutonium(IV) phases in acidic conditions. Their structural features, as deduced from low-temperature XAS investigations, will also be outlined. EXAFS data at the Pu-L_{III} edge strongly suggest the presence of Pu₆O₈ cores bridged together by the carboxylate moieties of the protonated ligands.

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Design of cage metal complexes as topological drugs, antifibrillogenic agents, paramagnetic and luminescent probes

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Cage metal complexes have found use in diagnostics and therapy due to their unique physicochemical properties, such as an almost complete isolation of an encapsulated metal ion from external factors, high (photo)chemical stability and chemical availability. Apical and ribbed functionalization of cage frameworks may also add other features, e.g. target delivery to a given biological system. Functionalization of cage metal complexes with linker groups ensures their binding with antibodies, proteins, peptides, oligonucleotides, oligosaccharides, liposomes by using enzymatic and immunochemical methods. We have developed [1–5] conventional synthetic procedures towards cage metal complexes with pre-designed, biological target–matching molecular structure and properties based on reactive clathrochelate precursors (Scheme) as molecular scaffolds for highly efficient functionalization reactions (nucleophilic and free-radical substitution, electrophilic addition, metal-promoted (catalyzed) homo- and cross-coupling reactions).

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The role of the HypA loop sequence in binding Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺

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Bacteria *Helicobacter pylori*, colonizing the human gastric mucosa, can cause gastritis, peptic ulcers and stomach cancer. It is estimated that half of the global population is infected by these bacteria. The presence of a nickel dependent enzyme – urease, enables successful colonization of the acidic conditions of the human stomach environment by *H. pylori*. Urease neutralizes gastric acid around a bacterium cell by catalysing the hydrolysis of the urea to ammonia and carbon dioxide [1].

HypA protein, together with HypB, delivers Ni²⁺ into [NiFe] hydrogenase, but it is also required for urease maturation. Besides nickel binding site, HypA has a structural zinc binding domain which forms a loop consisting of two conserved CXXC motifs separated by thirteen residues. Each of the motifs is accompanied by His residue. In the N-terminal site of the loop His is separated from CXXC by Ser and in the C-terminal site His is adjacent to the CXXC motif [1].

His and Cys residues are crucial for the Zn²⁺ binding process. Zn²⁺ is coordinated by two thiols and two imidazoles at an acidic pH, which occurs when the bacterium cell is subjected to acid shock, while at a neutral pH four thiols are involved in the metal ion binding. Interestingly, it has been found that pH-dependent alterations in the zinc domain have impact on the nickel binding site. This observation has led to the hypothesis that there is communication between the zinc and nickel site. The zinc domain acts as a pH sensor, which provides correct delivery of Ni²⁺ to a target protein [2].

Studies on the Ac-ELECKDCSHVFKPNALDYGVCEKCHS-NH₂ fragment of the loop region from *H. pylori* have also shown pH-dependent changes in the Zn²⁺ coordination [3]. Further studies on various modification of the HypA loop fragment have revealed the role of the residues in the linker between the CXXC motifs and the effect of the linker length on the stability of the complexes formed with Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺ ions. Pro residue, which is situated between the two CXXC motifs, has an important role in the metal ions binding ability of the loop, lowering efficacy of the metal ion coordination. However, reduction of the linker length between the CXXC motifs remarkably improves the binding efficacy of the loop [4].

Studies on the peptides containing only one of the CXXC motifs flanked by His residue and their analogues without His, have provided more details about the differences between CXXC motifs and the role of His residues in binding ability of the loop. In case of Zn²⁺ the N-terminal site (His separated from Cys by Ser: CXXCSH motif) is more effective than the C-terminal site (His next to Cys: CXXCH motif). Reverse situation has been observed for Cd²⁺; here the peptides with the C-terminal motif have a better coordination ability compared to

those with the N-terminal, regardless of whether His is in the sequence or not. This suggests that the adjacent residues may have an impact on the complexes stability [4].

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A novel ternary complex emphasizes the depletion of basicity in the N3-acyclovir donor atom within the main Cu(II)-acyclovir binding pattern.

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Structural studies on metal complexes with the acyclic nucleoside acyclovir (acv, see scheme) reveal four distinct metal binding patterns (MBP) [1]: (a) the formation of the M-N7 bond, (b) the cooperation between the M-N7 bond and one X-H...O6(acv) H-bond, with X being O-(aqua, methanol or ethanol) or N-(amino from ethylenediamine, glygly or cyclam) coordinated atom, (c) the M-(N7,O6) bidentate chelating mode and (d) the μ_2 -M₂-N7,O(ol) bridging mode, with O(ol) being the O-alcohol atom from the N9-pendant arm. All these MBP feature the formation of the metal-N7(acv) coordination bond. To date, the most common MBP for acv is (b). Our research group is focused in defining the frontiers of the coordination abilities of acv within mixed-ligand copper(II) complexes [2,3]. To this regard, some surprising results have been recently reported [3].

Synthesis and crystal structure of the novel compound. Attempts to obtain the ternary Cu(II)-DEA-acv complex (DEA = diethanolamine) only yielded a few well-shaped greenish crystals of the compound (H₃O)₂[Cu(acv)₂(H₂O)₂(SO₄)₂·2H₂O (**1**, 100 K, monoclinic system, space group *P*2₁/*c*, final *R*₁ 0.045). The centrosymmetric anion (see Fig. 1) have symmetry related pairs of O-aqua, N7-acv and O-sulfate donor atoms featuring a rather typical elongated-octahedral Cu(II) coordination, type 4+2, with bond lengths 1.963(2), 2.018(2) and 2.427(2) Å respectively.

Scheme. Acyclovir (acv).

Fig 1. Centro-symmetric anion in compound **1** (symmetry code $a = -x, 1-y, -z$).

Structural correlation between the copper(II) coordination polyhedron and the MBP of acv. The rather short Cu-O(aqua) bonds strongly favor to the cooperation of each Cu-N7(acv) bond with an intra-molecular interligand (aqua)O1-H1B...O6(acv) interaction (2.615(3) Å, 157.3°). This fact drives the coordination of the sulfate anions towards the apical sites. Thus, **1** exhibits the most common MBP of acv ligand (see Figure 1).

Crystal packing and other weak inter-molecular interactions involved in the crystal. The crystal of **1** consists of 2D frameworks (parallel to the *bc* plane) of H-bonded cations where the (aqua)O-H and N1-H(acv) groups act as H-donors for O6(acv) and three O-sulfate atoms. These layers are strongly reinforced by multi- π,π -stacking interactions (along the *c* axis) between six-membered rings of guanine-acv residues (inter-centroid distance d_{c-c} 3.42 Å, inter-planar distance $d_{\pi-\pi}$ 3.38 Å, inter-planar dihedral angle α 3.0°, slipping angles β or γ 8.12° or 9.32°). The N9-pendant arm of acv ligands fall oriented towards the external faces of these layers, which connect to each other by additional H-bonds. The terminal alcoholic group O(14)-H(14) is involved in the O14-H14...O(16, sulfate) and (H₃O⁺)O2-H2...O14(acv) interactions. Further H-bonds involving the H₃O⁺ ion and crystallization water link the referred layers in a 3D crystal.

Concluding remarks. In the novel compound, the most common MBP of acv is featured: the Cu-N7(acv) bond is assisted by an intra-molecular interligand (aqua)O-H...O6(acv) interaction. The apical Cu(II) coordination of the sulfate(2-) ligands and the equatorial binding of aqua ligands are also favored. The presence of two H₃O⁺ cations per complex anion in **1** emphasizes the deep depletion of basicity (proton affinity) in the N3-acv atom. Note that the remarkable steric hindrance imposed on N3 by the adjacent exocyclic -N(2)H₂ group and the acyclic N9-pendant arm minimizes the metal binding possibilities for this N3-acv heterocyclic atom.

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Novel dual band acid-base indicators based on Ni(II) or Cu(II) coordination compounds with vitamin B₆

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Metal coordination to biologically active molecules can be used in order to enhance their biological activity. Therefore, numerous studies regarding the interactions between important bioligands with several cations such as Co(III), Ni(II) or Cu(II) and their total characterization have reported in the literature [1]. In particular the bivalent ions such as nickel and copper as coordinating centers have become interest to researchers. Ni(II), classified as a borderline metal ion, forms stable coordination compounds with soft donor atoms, like nitrogen or sulphur, and with hard donors, like oxygen. Literature data focused mainly on the binding of Ni(II) through nitrogen atoms from proteins and peptides or through sulphur from thiol group of cysteine as the thermodynamically favored donor ligands for Ni(II) [2]. Cu(II) ion has exhibited a wide variety of coordination geometries in complexes with chelate ligands with hexadentate [3] or pentadentate-coordinated [4] ligands prepared and characterized crystallographically. Studies of Cu(II) complexes in these form have a value-added perspective in a view of their current development in bio-medicinal or pharmaceutical imaging, where stability of the Cu(II) chelate complex is crucial.

Acid–base titrations is a routine approach used in medicinal chemistry to determine pK_a values. With the knowledge of the pK_a, distribution plots can be calculated to show ionization degree of a potential drug candidate at physiological pH value (7.40). Properties such as lipophilicity, solubility, and permeability through membranes are pH-dependent and must be optimized during drug development process. Considering the fact that acid-base issue has attracted significant interest in chemistry, biology and in medicine. Therefore our research group has had a meaningful attribution in this field regarding the synthesis and the application as acid-base indicators of a new metal(II) complexes with vitamin B₆.

The assembly of four coordination compounds have been achieved, [Cu(O₂NO)(pm)₂]NO₃, [Cu(O₂NO)(pn)₂]NO₃, [Ni(pm)₂]Cl₂ and [Ni(pl)₂]Cl₂ (**Figure 1**), where *pm*, *pn*, and *pl* denote, respectively, pyridoxamine, pyridoxine, and pyridoxal. Moreover, the acid-base properties of new Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes, in aqueous solution by using two independent techniques: spectrophotometry and potentiometry, were determined and discussed. The reversed-titration method was used to show the maximum protonated state or to expand the scale of pH during titration. It was found that the protonated complexes studied undergo two-step dissociation process with the individual color change /reversible reactions; the color depends on protonation state of the Ni(II) or Cu(II) complexes/.

Figure 1. Ni(II) complexes studied with pyridoxamine (a) and pyridoxal (b) as ligands. The structures were obtained with CsChem3D Ultra – 12 program package using a MM2 force field *in vacuo*.

Based on the results of our experimental studies it could be concluded that among other metal(II) coordination compounds, the primary forms of complexes studied undergo readily protonation in acidic solution. They exist in dynamic equilibrium depending on the pH. This behavior should be their positive attribute with a large number of their applications as acid-base indicators in chemical laboratories or in medical tests.

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Synthesis and metal ion complexation studies of new polytopic aza-scorpionand receptors.

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Multitopic ligands have received an increasing interest in the last years because of their potential applications in fields such as molecular recognition, molecular devices, enzyme mimicking, and pharmaceutical chemistry. [1] In the Supramolecular Chemistry Group of the University of Valencia, we have been working in polytopic metal complexes acting as enzyme mimics. [2]

Here we report on two novel synthetic ligands, **L1** and **L2**, each with two different coordination sites. This fact provides the possibility to obtain complexes presenting different stoichiometries and coordination environments, and also hetero-bimetallic complexes (Scheme 1).

pH-metric titrations were performed to determine the speciation of Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Mn^{2+} complexes with **L1** and **L2** resulting in the formation either of mononuclear and binuclear complexes. Also the formation of hetero-metallic complex of **L2** with Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} has been studied in solution by pH-metric titration, the **L2**- Cu^{2+} - Zn^{2+} complex crystallized as pale blue crystals allowing us to determine the crystal structure by X-Ray diffraction as well as its composition by EDX technique (Scheme 1).

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Binding Ability of Diethylenetriamine-N,N,N',N'',N''-Pentakis-(Methylenephosphonic) Acid toward Biologically, Environmentally and Technologically Relevant Cations

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Cation chelation is a key process in a wide number of sectors, and many chelating agents are extensively used for many purposes. In this light, (organo)phosphonates proved very promising in the replacement of classical “complexones” (like, *e.g.*, EDTA), so that the number of applications of these chelants and their metal complexes is now very broad: agriculture, environmental science, magnetic resonance imaging, nanomaterials, radiopharmaceuticals, scale inhibition, waste management, and many others. This versatility is due to several reasons, such as: i) their chemical stability (also to breakdown by enzymatic hydrolysis), ii) their strong structural relationship to natural compounds together with their (generally) low toxicity, iii) the ease of synthesis of many diverse ligands (favored by the simplicity of attaching the phosphonate group to the organic moiety), and, iv) their solution properties (including their binding ability toward several cations). The last aspect is of great concern, since chemical speciation studies of (organo)phosphonate complexes are of extreme importance in many technological and industrial processes, as well as the environmental, biological and medical fields [1,2].

Among (organo)phosphonates, Diethylenetriamine-N,N,N',N'',N''-Pentakis-(Methylenephosphonic) Acid, DTPMPA, appears to be one of the most powerful chelants and it is now employed in many applications where strong metal chelation is desirable, owing to the frequent absence of precipitation of some of its complexes.

Chart 1. DTPMPA Structure.

In order to optimize its performances in many different systems, the modeling of its chemical speciation over a wide range of conditions (pH, temperature, ionic strength, composition) is needed, and this requires the use of a consistent number of stability constants and other thermodynamic formation parameters. Since the reliability of the modeling is also dependent on that of thermodynamic data used, accurate values must be available in many experimental conditions.

Unfortunately, as also reported by IUPAC in one of their technical reports dedicated to the stability of organophosphonate complexes, literature data related to DTPMPA speciation are of generally poor quality, owing to the use of the “impure” ligand during measurements (purity rarely above 60-75%) [1]. That is why we recently undertook a new systematic study on the speciation in aqueous solution of DTPMPA obtained by an efficient synthetic procedure, which allowed us to reach purities of about 95%, but, chiefly, without “interfering” impurities (*i.e.*, structurally similar compounds and/or free phosphoric acid) [2]. After the determination of its acid–base properties and alkali and alkaline earth metal complex formation in many ionic strength and temperature conditions, in the present contribution we report, as an extension of this study, some preliminary results on the binding ability of DTPMPA toward a series of biologically, environmentally and technologically relevant cations, such as: Sn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Fe^{3+} and Al^{3+} . Measurements have been performed mainly at $T = 298.15$ K in $\text{NaCl}_{(\text{aq})}$ at $I = 0.1$ mol dm^{-3} , though different conditions have also been investigated for some selected systems. Based on the stability constants determined, the sequestering ability of DTPMPA toward these cations has been also quantified by means of the calculation of $\text{pL}_{0.5}$ values in various conditions.

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DNA binding and nuclease activity of two Quinones and their Ruthenium complex counterparts

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Current studies have shown that 1 out of 3 people will develop some sort of cancer during their lives [1]. The treatment of cancer often requires chemotherapy, hence a deal of effort has been focused on the development of antitumour drugs. For most anticancer therapies, DNA is the primary target molecule, thereby development of small molecules able to interact with DNA has attracted much attention over the last decades [2]. In this context, bifunctional molecules bearing an aromatic moiety and a transition metal site have shown a deal of promise.

In this work, the syntheses of two dinuclear Ru (II) complexes is reported using quinones as bridging ligands (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Naphthazarin structure(A), Quinizarin (B), RuN (C) y RuQ (D).

The difference in the DNA mode of binding of two quinones, Naphtazarin and Quinizarin, and their respective dinuclear ruthenium complexes have been determined by thermodynamic and kinetic approaches using UV–Vis spectrophotometry, circular dichroism (CD), fluorescence spectroscopy, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), viscosity measurements and cleavage electrophoresis. The set of results collected show that the two quinones are able to intercalate into DNA even if Quinizarin displays the highest affinity. By contrast, the ruthenium dinuclear complexes can form bifunctional covalent-intercalated complexes, with the ligand partially intercalated into the DNA base-pairs and the metal covalently bound to the N7 guanine site.

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Homo- and heteroleptic metal complexes of bisphosphonates targeting enzymes of the isoprenoid biosynthetic pathway and/or DNA

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Bisphosphonates (BPs) are the most commonly prescribed drugs for the treatment of osteoporosis and other bone illnesses. In addition, some of these drugs have also shown antitumoral and antiparasitic activity [1]. In the search of improving the pharmacological profile of commercial bisphosphonates our group has developed first row transition metal complexes of risedronate, alendronate and pamidronate (figure 1). Obtained complexes were more active *in vitro* against *Trypanosoma cruzi*, ethiological agent of Chagas disease, than the free BPs and they resulted selective inhibitors of the parasitic enzyme farnesyl diphosphate synthase (*Tc*FPPS) [2].

Figure 1. Some commercial bisphosphonates (acid forms)

Based on these promising results, we extended our studies to the bisphosphonate ibandronate (IBA, figure 1) and developed heteroleptic palladium complexes including phenanthroline or bipyridine as co-ligands. Complexes of the formula $[M^{II}(IBA)(H_2O)_4]Cl$, with $M = Co, Mn, Ni$ and $[Pd(BP)_2(N-N)] \cdot 2NaCl$ with $BP = alendronate$ or $pamidronate$ and $N-N = phenanthroline$ or $bipyridine$ were synthesized and fully characterized. All obtained complexes were evaluated *in vitro* against amastigote form of *T. cruzi* resulting much more active than the corresponding BP ligands and being non toxic to mammalian cells up to 50-100 μM . Complexes were inhibitors of *Tc*FPPS and in particular, IBA complexes did not inhibit human FPPS presenting a selective antiparasitic activity. In addition, all complexes resulted good inhibitors of another parasitic enzyme of the isoprenoid biosynthetic pathway:

solaneyl-diphosphate synthase (*TcSPPS*). For the palladium mixed-ligand species including DNA intercalating compounds as co-ligands, human FPPS inhibitory effect was also observed. Therefore, biological activity against tumor cell lines (human lung adenocarcinoma A549 and human osteosarcoma MG-63) was also studied. Phenanthroline compounds were the most active palladium complexes both in tumors and in parasites. Based on these results, we propose that the mechanism of action of the mixed ligand species could be related to DNA-binding mediated by the intercalating ligands. In these sense, interaction of these complexes with calf thymus DNA was studied through fluorescence experiments using ethidium bromide as competitive intercalating agent. In fact, a strong quenching on the fluorescence of DNA-EB adduct was observed for both complexes containing phenanthroline as ligand while no effect of the bipyridine ones was detected. These rationally designed compounds are goods candidates for further studies and good leaders for future developments.

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Metal Complexes of Polyazamacrocyclic Ligands as Surface Functionalities of Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotubes.

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Many applications of carbon nanotubes depend on their functionalization. There are two general procedures for inserting chemical functionalities on their surface: the covalent and the non-covalent ones [1]. The non-covalent, or supramolecular, method is commonly accomplished by surface adsorption of the functionalities by means of weak forces. It was recently shown that nitroso-amino-pyrimidine residues are efficient anchor groups for irreversible attachment on the graphitic surface of activated carbon via π -stacking interactions [2]. Taking advantage of such anchor groups, we have synthesized three new ligands containing macrocyclic polyamine units (HL1-HL3, Figure 1) to be

Figure 1

employed in the surface functionalization of multi walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNs).

Ligand basicity and metal ion binding properties of HL1-HL3 were studied by means of potentiometric and UV-Vis spectrophotometric measurements performed in 0.1 M NMe₄Cl solution at 298.1 K.

The basicity of these molecules is consistent with the properties of their constituents, including protonation of the nitroso pyrimidine group, in very acidic solutions, and

deprotonation of the NH group linked to the pyrimidine ring, in very alkaline media.

HL1-HL3 bind metal ions such as Cu(II) and Zn(II) forming complexes of various stoichiometries. All three ligands give rise to ML^+ , MHL^{2+} and $MHLOH^+$ ($M = Cu, Zn$) species, the most stable ones being the ML^+ complexes involving the deprotonated ligand form (L^-). In the case of HL2 and HL3 also protonated MH_2L^{3+} species are formed. The stability of the ML^+ complexes is significantly high, $\log K$ values ranging from 20.9(1) to 24.5(5) for CuL^+ and from 16.3(1) to 19.1(4) for ZnL^+ ($L = L1-L3$), and is consistent with the macrocyclic nature of the ligands. HL1 is the ligand forming the most stable complexes, in agreement with the presence in its structure of a cyclam (1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradecane) ring. Also in agreement with the cyclam-based structure of HL1, both formation and dissociation of its metal complexes are characterized by some kinetic inertness.

The complex $[Cu(HL2)](ClO_4)_2$ was obtained in crystalline form and its crystal structure was determined by means of single crystal X ray diffraction. The structure is composed of polymeric

$\{[\text{Cu}(\text{HL}2)]^{2+}\}^n$ chains and ClO_4^- anions. A portion of this chain is shown in Figure 2 (bond distances are in Å). The metal ion has an octahedral coordination environment formed by the four macrocyclic nitrogen atoms and by two donor atoms of the pyrimidine unit of a contiguous complex molecule acting as bidentate ligand. Interestingly, one of the ClO_4^- anions forms close anion- π interactions with the electron deficient pyrimidine ring.

Figure 2

The three ligands are irreversibly adsorbed on the surface of MWCNs, as schematically depicted in Figure 3. Adsorption of HL1-HL3 was performed in aqueous solutions at pH 4 and 7.5. The adsorption isotherms performed at 298.1 K denoted maximum adsorption capacity of 0.55, 0.27, 0.31 mmol/g at pH 4 and 0.43, 0.29, 0.25 mmol/g at pH 7.5 for HL1, HL2 and HL3, respectively.

The hybrid material obtained upon adsorption of HL2 on a MWCN was isolated and used to bind Cu(II) ions from aqueous solution. It demonstrated enhanced ability in the adsorption of the metal ion relative to the unfunctionalized MWCN, its maximum adsorption capacity for Cu(II) being 0.26 mmol/g (0.12 mmol/g for pure MWCN). We are currently testing this metal-based hybrid material as a catalyst for Sonogashira reactions.

Figure 3

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POSTER COMMUNICATIONS

Thermodynamic and Kinetic Study of Mono- and Bis-triazamacrocyclic Ligands and their Transition Metal Complexes Mimicking Hydrolytic Enzyme Activity

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Polyaza-macrocyclic ligands are recently utilized to bind some radioisotopes for application in medicinal chemistry (^{60–64,67}Cu, ^{66–68}Ga, ^{86,90}Y, ¹¹¹In) [1,2] and the formed metal complexes of high thermodynamic stability and kinetic inertness are required for their use *in vivo* for medical purposes [1, 2]. Several copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes of bis-polyaza-macrocyclic ligands catalyse some chemical reactions and therefore they can be used as model systems mimicking enzymes activity [3, 4].

Scheme. The structural formulas of studied macrocyclic ligands

In this work, the protonation constants of novel macrocyclic ligands (see Scheme) as well as stability constants of their copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes were determined by glass-electrode potentiometry and molecular absorption spectroscopy. The formation of the copper(II) complexes of both ligands is accelerated with increased pH. The dissociation of both copper(II) complexes does not differ within experimental error indicating no cooperative effect for binucleating ligand. However, both complexes demonstrate significant catalytic activity in hydrolysis of model phosphodiester compounds.

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Synthesis, Characterization, Potentiometric study and DFT calculations of a Cobalt(II) complex with a 5- pyrazolone ligand

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The synthesis of a 5-pyrazolone derivative H₂L, bearing a carbothioamide moiety at N₁ position (Figure 1), has been conducted using a heteropoly acid as a catalyst. The complexation of Co(II) with this interesting N,S bidentate ligand, has been studied by potentiometry. This study suggested the formation of the two species in solution, [Co(HL)]⁺ and [Co(HL)₂], for which the stability constants have been determined.

Fig.1. Structure of the ligand H₂L

The complex is then synthesized, and fully characterized by IR, UV/Visible, MS, EPR, magnetic measurements, and electrochemistry. In order to investigate the most plausible structure, in accordance with all the analytical results, a theoretical study has been carried out using DFT calculations with Jaguar software.

All the results indicate a high spin Co(II) complex in an octahedral geometry around the metal ion. The pyrazolone acts as a monodeprotonated bidentate ligand, coordinated to the central metal through the amine nitrogen of the pyrazolone ring, and the sulfur of the thioamide moiety. The coordination is completed by two water molecules resulting in the general formula [Co(HL)₂.(H₂O)₂].

Mechanism of a Pd(II)/porphyrin complex formation and studies on its interaction with polynucleotides

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Interactions of synthetic and natural nucleic acids with porphyrins have been intensively investigated since the discovery in 1979 that these compounds are able to intercalate into DNA [1]. The flat aromatic structure of porphyrins, both free and in form of metal complexes, coupled with their high absorptivity, make these substances especially suitable for investigations on the mechanisms of drug binding to nucleic acids; moreover, introduction of a metal ion converts a porphyrin into a metallo-intercalator with additional properties [2]. In recent years the field of porphyrin and metal-porphyrin chemistry has expanded significantly, mainly in connection with the use of these molecules in biology and for light harvesting and energy conversion [3,4]. DNA/porphyrin systems have been analysed using very different methods but many details of the binding still need to be elucidated.

We present here a combined thermodynamic and kinetic analysis of the formation of the Pd(II) complex of 5,10,15,20-tetrakis(1-methyl-4-pyridyl)-porphyrine (Figure 1) and of its interaction with DNA.

Figure 1: Pd(II) complex of 5,10,15,20-tetrakis(1-methyl-4-pyridyl)-porphyrine.

The kinetic analysis of the binding of the Pd(II) to 5,10,15,20-tetrakis(1-methyl-4-pyridyl)-porphyrine confirms 1:1 binding stoichiometry and quantitative reaction. As concerns the binding of the complex to DNA, fluorescence and absorbance titrations under different conditions of temperature and salt content concur in indicating that the binding is strong. Kinetic and

equilibrium parameters for the complex interaction with the nucleic acid are obtained and the binding mechanism is discussed. An intercalative binding mode is found to be operative.

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Cu(II)-Bispidine Complexes for Nuclear Medicine and Diagnosis

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Positron emission tomography (PET), combined with X-ray computed tomography (CT) scanning, currently provides some of the most accurate information on tumor distribution of many common cancers. Yet, commonly used positron emitters such as ^{11}C and ^{18}F show limitations due to their limited half life ($t_{1/2} = 20$ and 110 min, respectively) and their often complex and demanding synthesis. Thus, ^{64}Cu ($t_{1/2} = 12.7$ h, β^+ , 17.8%, 653 keV, β^- , 38.4%, 579 keV) and ^{67}Cu ($t_{1/2} = 61.8$ h, β^- , 189 keV (20%), 154 keV (22%), 121 keV (57%)) have been identified as a promising radionuclide pair for the future of PET imaging and targeted radiotherapy for cancer.

We present a detailed physicochemical study of new ligands, part of a bispidine series [1], showing promising qualities towards Cu(II) complexation in terms of thermodynamics, kinetics and electrochemistry.[2] Their rigid skeleton provides them with a pre-organized structure for the coordination of Cu(II) which leads to an optimized complexation for TEP imaging (Figure 1). Selected ligands were then tested for isotopic labeling and also coupled to relevant biological targeting molecules like biotin (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Biotine-coupled bispidine chelator

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Antitumor Properties and Nuclease Activity of Platinum(II) Complexes Based on Hidroxyquinoline Ligands in a Human Osteosarcoma Cell Line and Plasmid DNA

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Despite the remarkable success of CDDP (cisplatin) [1] in the treatment of different types of cancers, two major limitations of the drug are of concern (i) its dose-limiting effects and (ii) inactivity against some of the most frequent human tumour types. Thus, the necessity for the search of structural analogues endowed with fewer side effects and capable of overcoming acquired resistance to CDDP has arisen. The hydroxyquinolines derivatives have medicinal properties such as antineurodegenerative, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer activities [2]. In this project we studied the anticancer properties, mechanism of action and nuclease activity of two platinum(II) complexes (**1** and **2**) with analogous of quinolines in a human osteosarcoma cell line (MG-63) and with plasmid DNA (pDNA, pA1).

Based on the results of proliferation and cytotoxic assays (crystal violet and MTT assays) it was observed that after 6 h complex **2** caused a cell viability inhibition at 10-100 μM while **1** did not show any effects in the same range of concentrations ($p < 0.01$). At 24 h compound **2** inhibited cell viability at 5-100 μM while complex **1** induced this effect at 50-100 μM ($p < 0.01$). Interestingly, compound **2** caused a more pronounced antiproliferative effect than CDDP on the human osteosarcoma cell line (IC_{50} 4 μM vs. 43 μM).

The genotoxic effects of complex **1** and **2** in MG-63 cells were examined using the comet assay. The results reveal single and double-strand DNA breaks. Complex **2** promoted a significant genotoxic effect in MG-63 cells at 1 μM , comparing to the less distinct one obtained at 2.5-5 μM ($p < 0.01$). The decrease in DNA damage as the complex concentration increases may be due to overt cytotoxicity exerted on this cell line. Complex **1** only caused a genotoxic effect from 2.5 to 5 μM ($p < 0.01$).

To better understand the possible mechanism involved in the cytotoxicity of **1** and **2** in MG-63 cells, we evaluated this effect on the oxidative stress and apoptosis. The complex **2** increased the level of reactive oxygen species (ROS) by 300% over basal at 25-100 μM , whereas no such effect was observed for **1** ($p < 0.01$). Moreover, complex **2** increased the level of early apoptotic cells (annexin V+/PI-) and diminished the mitochondrial membrane potential at 10-50 μM at 6 h of treatment.

Within the studies of the mechanism of action we present the results of the interaction of **1** and **2** with pA1 pDNA. No significant cleavage activity was observed for both complexes in MOPS buffer. The addition of oxone and MPA – strong oxidizing and reducing agents – did

not affect the extent of the DNA cleavage. In PBS buffer, however, both complexes seem to be more active. Complex **2** linearized pDNA at 50 μ M and upon addition of oxone the extent of the cleavage increased considerably. Complex **1** exhibits less activity, since it induced a double-strand cleavage only in the presence of oxone. These findings indicate that oxidative conditions are very important for the nuclease activity of these platinum compounds to take place.

Finally, the most dramatic effect on the antitumor activity was produced by the change from the monodentate quinoline ligand in complex **1** to the hydroxyquinolate N,O-chelate ligand in complex **2**. Complex **1** was much less active than CDDP or the chelate compound **2**, indicating that the forced planarity and the non-rotation around the N–Pt bond in compound **2** are most likely the key features in the witnessed antitumor effect and nuclease activity.

Altogether, our findings suggest that compound **2** is potentially the best candidate for the future use in alternative osteosarcoma treatments.

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Coordination versatility of phosphine derivatives of fluoroquinolones. New Cu^I and Cu^{II} complexes and their interactions with DNA.

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The term „antibiotics” refers to a group of natural, semi-synthetic or synthetic compounds with bacteriostatic or bactericidal properties. Nowadays, the group of antibiotics includes thousands substances with different chemical structures aimed at various molecular targets. Despite a large diversity of the available substances, the search for new compounds which would be more effective in killing or inhibiting the growth of microorganisms is still ongoing. This is a consequence of the ever increasing pathogens' resistance to antibiotics. This problem is of significance not only in view of the treatment of bacterial infections, but also fungal, viral or tumor diseases [1-5]. One of the ways to overcome drug resistance is the synthesis of analogues of already used substances, characterized by a higher or broader biological activity. Another possibility may be the synthesis of metal complexes with the existing drugs. Numerous literature reports state that coordination compounds often have better biological properties than uncoordinated drugs. Formation of a complex frequently changes the solubility, bioavailability and the mechanism of action of the parent molecule [6-10].

Herein, new copper(I) and copper(II) complexes with phosphine derivatives of two fluoroquinolone antibiotics – ciprofloxacin (HCp) and norfloxacin (HNr) are presented. Two copper(I) complexes, ([Cu^I-PCp] and [Cu^I-PNr]), were obtained in the reaction of phosphine derivative of ciprofloxacin (PCp) or norfloxacin (PNr) with cupric iodide and 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline (dmp). The water soluble copper(II) complexes ([OPCp-Cu^{II}]⁺ and [OPNr-Cu^{II}]⁺) are the result of the reaction of oxide derivatives of PCp (OPCp) or PNr (OPNr) with [Cu(phen)(NO₃)₂]. The synthesized compounds were characterized by elemental analysis and MS as well as by the NMR, EPR and IR spectroscopies. X-ray techniques were used to determine the crystal and molecular structures of complexes with HCp derivatives (Fig. 1).

The interactions of all the synthesized compounds, ligands and complexes, with deoxyribonucleic acid were determined. Unlike the uncoordinated ligands, the complexes caused the degradation of the DNA plasmid. In general, the complexes with HCp-based derivatives cleaved the plasmid less efficiently than the analogous compounds with an HNr moiety. The results of gel electrophoresis revealed that in the presence or absence of H₂O₂, the copper(I) complexes caused only a single-stranded cleavage of the sugar-phosphate backbone of DNA. In turn, the copper(II) complexes damaged the plasmid exclusively in the presence of the oxidant. The addition of H₂O₂ caused distinct changes in the plasmid structure, resulting in a complete disappearance of its native form. Forms II and III arising from a single- and double-strand cleavage were detected. Studies of the interactions with calf thymus DNA in the presence of ethidium bromide (EB) showed that the tested complexes and

phosphines interact with DNA in a partial intercalation mode, contrary to unmodified antibiotic and oxide derivatives, which do not displace EB from the system.

Fig. 1. X-ray structures of [Cu^I-PCp] and [OPCp-Cu^{II}]⁺ and their interactions with DNA.

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Zn^{II}(salGly)(phenantroline) complexes – synthesis, characterization and cytotoxicity

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The development of metal drugs containing bio-relevant metal ions is an area of current interest. The underlying principle is that the metal ion homeostasis of such metals will be better dealt by human physiology, causing less damaging side effects. Zinc is the second most abundant transition metal in the human body. Due to Zinc's numerous physiological roles, Zn(II) complexes have been used as DNA binders, radioprotective agents, tumor photosensitizers, besides demonstrating insulin-mimetic, antibacterial and antimicrobial activities. [1] In recent years Zn(II) complexes have been gathering attention as potential anticancer agents with lower toxicity *in vivo*, with probably distinct targets and modes of action from the classical metallodrugs. [2, 3]

Combining the metal ion with bioactive and/or bioavailable organic ligands can contribute to more effective and more selective metallodrugs. Schiff base metal complexes have been extensively studied due to their ease of preparation and versatility. Polypyridyl complexes have been intensively studied for their features as DNA intercalators, as well as their potential cytotoxicity. [4] Metal complexes using ligands based on phenanthroline derivatives are reported to be active against various pathologic conditions including cancer, microbial and fungal infections. [5]

Our group has been devoted to the search for prospective metal-based anticancer drugs. [6, 7] With this objective in mind a series of zinc(II) complexes with the general formula

[Zn(SalGly)(NN)] were prepared, where salGly is the Schiff base resulting from condensation of glycine and salicylaldehyde and NN is phenanthroline (phen) or a phenanthroline derivative:
5-chloro-1,10-phenanthroline (Clphen),
1,10-phenanthroline-5-amine (aminophen), bathophenanthroline (Bphen), 5,6-Epoxy-5,6-dihydro-[1,10]-phenanthroline (epoxyphen), bathocuproin sulfonate disodium salt hydrate (BCS); bathophenanthroline disulfonic acid disodium salt hydrate (BPS).

Figure 1 – General structure expected for the complexes

The complexes were characterized in the solid state and in solution by elemental analysis, infrared (FTIR), UV/Vis absorption, and NMR spectroscopies. Crystals suitable for single-crystal X-ray diffraction studies were obtained, showing the neutral complex adopting a dinuclear structure with both zinc atoms hexacoordinated. One zinc atom is bound to two SalGly ligands and the other to two phenanthroline moieties and two phenolate O-atoms. The phenolate O-atoms are shared between the two zinc atoms. The cytotoxicity of the complexes

was assessed against human tumor cells namely ovarian (A2780), breast (MCF7) and cervical (HeLa), as well as in a non-tumoral embryonic kidney (HEK) cell line. In general, the precursor $[\text{Zn}(\text{SalGly})] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ presents much lower cytotoxicity ($\text{IC}_{50} \sim 200 \mu\text{M}$) than the synthesized phenanthroline complexes in all cell lines studied, which emphasizes the active contribution of the phenanthroline ligand to the bioactivity of the complexes.

Figure 2 - Molecular structure obtained for $[\text{Zn}(\text{SalGly})(\text{Bphen})]$.

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Speciation of trivalent metal ions with dehydroacetic acid in aqueous solution: a multi-instrumental approach

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Pyran-2-one derivatives such as dehydroacetic acid (3-acetyl-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-2H-pyran-2-one = L) are widely utilized as antibacterials in food and cosmetic products.[2] The complexing properties of the dehydroacetic acid towards numerous bi and trivalent cations have been well studied at the solid state and in mixed solvents,[2] whereas there are few data on speciation in aqueous solution. The interaction of L with M^{3+} (M: Al, Fe, La and Gd) has been investigated by the use of various methods: Potentiometry, 1H and ^{13}C Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR), Raman and Infrared Spectroscopy (IR) and Molecular Fluorescence Spectroscopy. Potentiometric measurements were carried out in solutions 0.1 M $NaClO_4$, at 25 °C by a glass electrode at different concentration metal and ligand ratio (C_M/C_L).

Fig.1. Job plot for Fe^{3+} -L and Al^{3+} -L systems (ΔF is variation of fluorescence as a function of mole ratio ($r=C_M/(C_M+C_L)$))

Fig.2 Z_H (average number of protons Released per L) as a function of pH in solutions with $C_M/C_L = 1$.

The M^{3+} -L systems were investigated in the pH range 2-7; for higher values, solid phases were formed. Data processing suggests the formation of complex species with a 1:2 ratio for Fe and 1:1 ratio for Al, La and Gd. 1H -NMR and Raman data suggest carbonyl and hydroxylic groups are coordinated to the metal ions.

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Structure and coordination properties of imidazole-based bicycles appended with acetate groups

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Synthetic bicyclic heterocycles gain substantial interest in medicinal chemistry due to structural similarity to many natural products. This makes them capable of binding to multiple biological targets with high affinity and providing pharmaceutical activities in essential cellular processes. In particular, imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine (IP) and imidazo[1,2-a]pyrimidine (IPM) are prevalent structural motifs in pharmaceutically and biologically active compounds, e.g. Zolpidem with IP ring is used for treatment of insomnia and Divaplon with IPM ring is an anticonvulsant drug.^[1,2] Numerous compounds based on imidazo[2,1-b]thiazole (ITZ) ring have also been reported to exhibit immunomodulatory, antihelmintic, antibacterial and anticancer properties. Surprisingly, there are only few reports in the literature describing coordination properties of imidazole-based bicyclic systems with specific functional groups.^[3]

This presentation shows crystal structures of imidazo[2,1-b]thiazol-2-yl (**1**), imidazo[1,2-a]pyrimidin-2-yl- (**2**) and imidazo[1,2-a]pyridin-3-ylacetic acids (**3**) (Fig. 1) and their complexes with selected 3d-metal ions. Impact of acid-base properties and position of acetate group on the bicyclic ring on the structures and physicochemical properties of ligands and complexes will be discussed.

Fig. 1. Ligands of interest used to obtain coordination compounds with 3d metal ions

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ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY OF HESPERETIN AND ITS ANALOGUES WITH PRIMARY AMINES

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Hesperetin (5,7,3-trihydroxyl-4-methyl-flavanone) is one of the flavonones that belong to flavonoid class of compounds, found in citrus fruits. Hesperetin has multiple biological and pharmacological activities, including antioxidant properties, inhibition of cancer development [1], and many others.

Besides, it has been demonstrated that hydrazone hesperetin Schiff base has exhibited deeper intercalation of DNA and cytotoxic activity than hesperetin itself [2, 3].

Schiff bases derived from the group of imines are widely distributed in many biological systems and they are used in medicine due to their pharmacological activities as antimalarial, anticancer, antibacterial, antifungal, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial and antiviral agents [4, 5].

Newly received Schiff bases (HHSB and HTSC) derive from hesperetin and benzoic acid hydrazide or thiosemicarbazide, respectively. The synthesized compounds have been characterized using appropriate of analytical techniques such: elemental analysis, thermal, magnetic, and spectral studies (IR, UV-visible, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR).

Figure 1: Chemical structure of hesperetin Schiff bases.

The synthesized compounds were screened for inhibition of radical species activity using DPPH[•], ABTS^{•+}, O₂^{•-} and OH[•]. The antioxidant activity of the Schiff bases was also analyzed in the simulated conditions of oxidative stress induced in liver mitochondria isolated from Wistar rats.

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Free Energies of Protonation and Complexation of Platinum and Vanadate Metal Ions with Naringin and Phenolic Acids: Theoretical Calculations Instead of Experimental Values Involving their bio relevance

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The Experimental thermodynamic equilibrium (pKa values) and stability constants ($\log \beta$) of vanadium and platinum binary and mixed ligand complexes involving naringin, ferulic acid, p-coumaric acid, caffeic acid, vanillic acid, sinapic acid, and gallic acid were determined at 310 °K in 0.16 mol.dm⁻³ NaNO₃ aqueous solutions using pH- potentiometric technique and by means of two estimation models (HYPERQUAD 2008 and Bjerrum-Calvin). The theoretical calculations of overall protonation and stability constants of the metal complex species in solution were predicted as the free energy change associated with the ligand protonation, and metal ion – ligand complex formation equilibria (species solvation/desolvation) using ab initio and density function theory (DFT) calculations. The usage of the experimental potentiometry technique and theoretical predictions provides a complete picture of the microscopic equilibria of the studied systems (vanadium/platinum – naringin – phenolic acid). Specifically, this theoretically DFT predications would be useful to determine the most real protonation constants of the studied bioligands in which the binding sites changes due to the ligand protonation/deprotonation equilibria. Also, the complexing capacities of vanadium and platinum towards naringin, ferulic acid, p-coumaric acid, caffeic acid, vanillic acid, sinapic acid, and gallic acid in solutions were evaluated and discussed. From the determined experimental stability constants of different metal complex species, the concentration distribution diagrams of the various metal ion complex species in solution was estimated using HySS 2009 software.

Kinetic modeling of Cr(VI) Sorption onto Exhausted Coffee from Cr(VI)-Cu(II) Binary Mixtures in a Stirred Batch Reactor

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In order to minimize the chemical or biological sludge generated from conventional processes and get the possibility of metal recovery, cost-efficient adsorption by readily available biomass has become a well-recognized detoxification process in the recent years. Attributable to the lignin moieties of fruit and vegetable wastes, which are reported to contain electron donor groups for Cr(VI) reduction to Cr(III) [1,2], both living and dead agricultural biomass have been successfully used as biosorbents for Cr(VI) removal in aqueous solutions.

In the present work, kinetics of Cr(VI) sorption onto exhausted coffee from Cr(VI)-Cu(II) binary mixtures has been studied in a stirred batch reactor. In order to get enough experimental data to model the process, two sets of experiments that differ by 10 times metal ions concentration range were carried out. Mole ratios of Cr(VI) and Cu(II) in both sets of binary mixtures were varied.

The model has been developed in basis to (i) irreversible reduction of Cr(VI) to Cr(III) reaction, whose reaction rate is assumed to be proportional to the concentration of Cr(VI) adsorbed and to the difference between the maximum amount of Cr(III) formed that can be found in solution (ii) adsorption and desorption of Cr(VI) and formed Cr(III) assuming that all the processes follow Sips type kinetics. The proposed model fits adequately the experimental data obtained with both binary mixtures concentration ranges studied. The model was validated by checking it against independent sets of data.

This research is a significant contribution in sorption modelling field and opens expectations for Cr(VI) biosorption in multi-metal solutions since it includes Cr(VI) reduction, Cr(VI) and Cr(III) sorption/desorption and effect of other metals on it. Furthermore, this work demonstrates that the established model can be validated by checking it against independent sets of data, a highly advisable method for researchers in the field of modelling to validate the models.

Figure 1. A scheme of Cr(VI) sorption/desorption, Cr(VI) reduction and Cr(III) sorption/desorption in the presence of Cu(II) and protons. ▲ and Δ indicate active sites.

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Sequestering ability of L-ascorbic acid towards bioavailable metal cations

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Interactions of L-ascorbic acid (Figure 1) with metal cations are known to play an important role in many biological systems [1]. The aqueous chemistry of L-ascorbic acid is of essential importance in understanding the characteristics of this water soluble vitamin. This ligand, being a good electron donor and an essential molecule in biological systems, acts as an effective antioxidant, protects living cells from damaging effects of reactive species such as reactive oxygen radicals. In the recent years, a great attention has been devoted to the interactions of biologically active molecules with various metal cations in order to determine the possibility of using these molecules in chelating therapy. However details about the complexation of L-ascorbic acid with some bioavailable metal cations are not known, particularly regarding the structure of these species [2-4].

Figure 1. L-Ascorbic acid (HL).

In this communication we report on a potentiometric study of the aqueous binary ligand complexes of Ni(II), Zn(II), Al(III) and Cr(III) with L-ascorbic acid. The study was conducted under physiological conditions, *i.e.* at an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm⁻³ NaCl and a temperature of 37.0 ± 0.1° C. The protonation constants of the free ligand and the stability constants of the binary ligand complexes were determined using pH titration data. The general equilibrium can be written, schematically, for all the four systems as follow:

which takes into account the possible formation of simple ($q=r$), mixed ($q \neq r$), mononuclear ($p=1$) and polynuclear ($p>1$) species. In the numerical treatments to evaluate the complexation constants, the acidic constants of L-ascorbic acid, determined by potentiometric measurements, as well as the equilibrium constants for the metal cations hydrolytical species, taken from literature [5], have been maintained invariant. The most probable p , q , r values and the corresponding constants β_{pqr} were computed by a numerical approach based on the least squares procedure using the program Hyperquad [6].

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Investigation of the chemistry of lanthanides based materials Ln(III)-MOFs with dicarboxylic acids

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Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) have been constantly arising as very important hybrid materials over the past two decades. Such materials place a wide range of potential applications on gas storage [1], gas capture [2], separation [3], chemical catalysis [4], luminescence [5], magnetism [6], and drug delivery [7]. The metal-organic framework materials based on lanthanides (Ln-MOFs) elicit increasing interest in the research area of metal-organic materials (MOF), due to their unique optical and magnetic properties and the distinct coordination profile of the lanthanide ions in complex compounds. The luminescent potential of lanthanide ions is interlinked to structural details of the coordination environment. Lanthanide MOFs can also project other important characteristics such as permanent porosity and nanoscale processibility. These notable luminescent features of lanthanides along with the unique properties of MOFs provide excellent possibilities for designing novel luminescent materials with enhanced functionalities and high added value for specific applications [8].

Herein, we report the study of the Ln-MOFs chemistry, in aqueous and organic environment, of three specific lanthanides (La(III), Nd(III) and Er(III)) with succinic acid. The result of the investigation of the binary and ternary system of Ln(II) with succinic acid was the syntheses and isolation of five new materials. All compounds were characterized by single crystal X-ray crystallography, FT-IR spectroscopy, elemental analysis, while extensive studies were carried out on their optical properties (luminescence). For all compounds, synthesis reactions, along with the FT-IR spectra, crystallographic data and elemental analysis provide evidence supporting their physicochemical identity. The new crystalline materials exhibit 3D micro porous structure, which grants them high selectivity, thereby rendering them highly promising for chemical sensor development, industrial and environmental applications.

Figure 1: Three dimensional presentation of the crystal lattices of the new materials

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Hydroxypyridinone as New Molybdenum Ion Buffers

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Molybdenum, an important co-factor of the nitrogen-fixing enzyme nitrogenase, essential for the nitrogen fixation process, is very rare in soils. Either it is present in a highly soluble form (MoO_4^{2-}), making it susceptible to leaching [1], or it is attached to organic matter and/or mineral surfaces in soils [2]. To overcome this, bacteria release small complexing agents (metallophores) that will allow the further uptake of molybdenum. In the present work, we intend to identify those natural metal chelators produced by the *Frankia sp.* bacteria. For that, and to mimic the natural metal sources in artificial media, we will use synthetic chelating agents aiming the development of a new molybdate buffer system, soluble, nontoxic, not taken up and stable under various physiological conditions.

In this communication we will present first results obtained using *hydroxypyridinone derivatives* as chelating agents. This family of ligands was selected taking into account, besides its known good ability as Mo(VI) chelators, its coordination similarities with the chelating groups of known natural siderophores: hydroxamic acids in case of ferrichrome and deferrioxamine, and catecholates in protochelin and enterobactin.

Considering all the species present in the bacterial growth media, solution speciation calculations were performed, aiming the optimization of the chelating agent concentration to the system that we intend to mimic.

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Silver Atomic Quantum Clusters (AQC's) inhibit the DNA/DOX interaction by conformational modification of DNA

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The development in recent years of new chemical methods for synthesizing nano materials has given way to the obtaining of silver nanoparticles and other types of silver compounds with potential applications in biomedicine. Due to the quantum confinement [1], silver nano clusters of low atomicity are precious species endowed with special properties and a wide range of potential applications [2, 3]. By combination of thermodynamic and kinetic measurements and theoretical calculations, we have reported that Ag₃ clusters interact with DNA through intercalation, inducing heavy structural modification to DNA [4]. Lifetime of Ag₃ clusters in the intercalated position is 2 to 3 orders larger than for classical organic intercalators like ethidium bromide or proflavine. Doxorubicin (DOX) (Figure 1), is a

prominent member of the anthracycline antibiotics family, one of the most effective types of anticancer drugs currently in use [5], whose interaction with DNA has been studied previously in our group [6]. To get a better insight into the clusters effect on DNA, we address here as an alternative model for such interactions the effect of the cluster and silver ions on the binding of DOX to DNA.

Figure 1. Structure of DOX

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CAGEDRUGS: Design and elaboration of novel topological drugs based on cage compounds

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The CAGEDRUGS project brings together five research centres (*Faculty of Chemistry University of Wrocław, Department of Chemistry National Taras Shevchenko University, Department of Chemistry Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Nesmeyanov Institute of Organoelement Compounds RAS, and Vernadskii Institute of General and Inorganic Chemistry NASU*) devoted to the development of new nanomaterials for biomedical use based on macrobicyclic cage metal complexes (clathrochelates) [1]. This joint exchange programme promotes and strengthens the complementarity of the participants and stimulates cross-fertilization, thus forming an excellent center of synergy in research, innovation and technology in the area of functional nanomaterials. This network offers a complete training in the synthesis and characterization of new cage metal-containing materials for biomedical applications.

During the course of the project a series of new clathrochelate compounds based on tris-dioximate (a) and tris-oxalodihydrazide (b) structures (Scheme 1) has been elaborated. Their design, synthesis and physico-chemical characteristics, as well as biological activities were performed in five work packages (WP1: Design and template synthesis, WP2: Identification and structure studies, WP3: Spectral and physico-chemical characterisation, WP4: Reactivity and functionalisation, WP5: Biomedical applications of cage compounds) [2].

Scheme 1. Tris-dioximate (a) and tris-oxalodihydrazide (b) clathrochelates. Supramolecular binding of bis-clathrochelate Fe(II) as effective inhibitor of T7 RNA polymerase (IC₅₀=500nM) to replicative fork by data of molecular docking (c).

The ability of clathrochelates to interact with proteins [3], their activity as transcription inhibitors of DNA and RNA polymerases (Figure 2) [4, 5] as well as anti-fibrillogenic activity [7] has been reported. It was shown that supramolecular complexes are formed by multicentered interactions between functionalized substituents in spatially determined positions of the clathrochelate cage framework and complementary protein groups, and by inclusion of the macrobicycle into the cavities of tertiary protein structure.

The joint research carried out in the frame of CAGEDRUGS project was due to an efficient collaboration and mobility of researchers from five research teams, sharing their expertise, knowledge and best practice. The laboratory activities with learning by doing, planning of scientific activities, participation to scientific lectures/group discussions/workshops and networking activities were main elements of training of Early Stage Researchers and transfer of knowledge.

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Specific binding modes of Cu(II) and Ag(I) with neurotoxic domain of human prion protein in presence of SDS micelles

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Neurodegenerative Prion diseases known as Transmissible Spongiform Encephalopathies (TSEs) are a group of fatal neuronal and to some extent infectious disorders associated with pathogenic protein agent called prion protein (PrP) [1]. The pathology results from the conformational change of the normal cellular form of prion protein (PrP^C) to an abnormal scrapie isoform (PrP^{Sc}) [2,3]. The two forms of PrP are identical in the primary structure, but different in the secondary structure that lead to changes of their physicochemical properties [4,5]. Unlike PrP^C, PrP^{Sc} is highly insoluble, protease resistant and highly prone to aggregate [1,6]. Elevated β -sheet content of PrP^{Sc} is essential for protein aggregation and formation of pathological deposits [7].

PrP^C is a neuronal membrane-anchored prion protein of unknown function. It consists of two distinct structural domains, the unstructured N-terminus and the globular C-terminal domain of well defined tertiary structure [8]. N-terminal domain contains four tandem repeats of PHGGGWGQ octapeptide sequence encompassing copper anchoring histidine residue [9]. Outside octarepeat domain, so called toxic region, following octarepeat domain hosts two independent Cu²⁺ binding sites, encompassing His-96 and His-111 residues, respectively [10].

Human prion protein fragment (hPrP) encompassing the 91-127 region, namely amyloidogenic (neurotoxic) domain, comprises two copper-binding sites corresponding to His-96 and His-111 residues. Our major goal was to explore the impact of the hydrophobic tail on the conformation of the amyloidogenic prion protein fragment and the modulatory role of metal ions binding. Although PrP^C function and the role of copper in TSEs is still unknown, number of reports indicate that copper binding to amyloidogenic region induces protein misfolding [11,12]. Our earlier molecular dynamics simulations (MD) study with hPrP91-127 PrP fragments indicate the strong peptide's propensity to β -sheet conformation, in particular strong in the segment located next to His-111 and C-terminal hydrophobic tail of the peptide. Contradictory behavior results indicating loss of secondary structure elements were observed in presence of Cu²⁺. This may suggest that Cu(II) eradicates peptide's natural β -sheet structural propensity [13].

Anionic surfactants are known of their high affinity to hydrophobic surfaces of proteins. Shielding of hydrophobic surfaces may result in changes of numerous properties of affected protein domain [14]. Cu²⁺ and Ag⁺ (probe for Cu⁺) interaction with hPrP91-127 in the absence and presence of anionic surfactant sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) is presented in this work. The coordination ability of amyloidogenic fragment is significantly different in the aqueous solution when compared to that containing SDS micelles. Addition of SDS into solution containing hPrP91-127 and its complexes with metal ions results in the formation of the α -

helical structure of the peptide backbone while in the case of aqueous solution random coil structure is observed [13]. The α -helical structure of the peptide spans the segment between His-111 and C-terminus, making imidazole side chain fixed in more rigid structure, while His-96 is in random conformation.

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Synthetic study of binary and ternary Ti(IV)-H₂O₂-(hydroxycarboxylate) systems in water. Correlation with hybrid prosthetic biomaterials.

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Titanium is a transition metal known for its special chemical reactivity profile and a dominant role in several applications. Its applications related to the improvement of human life quality are based on its chemical properties (excellent corrosion resistance, mechanical resistance, low density, easy to work with, low toxicity, biocompatibility and permeability of X-rays) [1]. Exemplified by such distinct physicochemical properties, it can enter a variety of metal free and metal-variable reactivity systems and in so doing it exhibits strong affinity to a variety of materials, including ceramics and resins.

It is a versatile metal with applications in many aspects of human life. In the form of TiO₂, it is encountered in variety of health products (cosmetics, sunscreens, laptops, bikes, jewelry etc.) and pharmaceuticals. It forms alloys with metals (Fe, Al, Mn, Mo) and in such a capacity it is encountered in numerous industrial and non-industrial applications. Due to its low toxicity and biocompatibility, titanium is used successfully in the manufacture of artificial prosthetic orthopedic implants, in cases of total/partial replacement of failed hard tissues, such as bone and ligaments in joints (considered physiologically inert), and b) dental and other implants of high quality [1]. Because of its conduct with human tissues, great interest has been recently focused upon the potential activity of titanium as an allergen agent [2,3,4].

In the present work, a study was launched to investigate a) binary systems Ti(IV) with organic α -hydroxy carboxylic acids (glycolic, lactic, alpha-hydroxy isobutyric, quinic acid, citric acid, etc.), and b) the ability to synthesize ternary Ti(IV) compounds with the above acids and H₂O₂. The effort reflects attempts to comprehend the behavior of that metal in its Ti(IV) oxidation state, often derived and generated under cellularly aberrant conditions or supplied as such in the form of various medicaments. The emerging new materials Ti(IV)-quinic acid and Ti(IV)-citrate-H₂O₂, with representative dinuclear and tetranuclear clusters, a) illustrate the contributions of the nature, structural-physical and chemical characteristics of the employed organic substrates in the synthesis and physicochemical characterization of binary hybrid titanium material, and b) reveal factors that could affect the biological activity-inactivity of biomaterials designed and manufactured to cover surgical prostheses [4].

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Spectroscopy and structure of Ln³⁺ complexes with naphthylsulfonylamidophosphates as new light converting molecular devices

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This work presents a detailed study of lanthanide complexes with dimethyl 2-naphthylsulfonylamidophosphate Na[Ln(L¹)₄] (**1Ln**) and bis(4-methylphenyl) 2-naphthylsulfonylamidophosphate Na[Ln(L²)₄] (**2Ln**) (where Ln = Eu³⁺, Gd³⁺, Tb³⁺ and Yb³⁺) in wide range of temperatures from 4 to 295 K with the aim to probe the specific energetic and structural characteristics that influence ligand-to-metal energy transfer and luminescence efficiency. The work focuses also on the role of the LMCT state on the ligand-to-metal energy transfer. Spectroscopic results of **1Ln** where [L¹]⁻=[(C₁₀H₇S(O)₂NP(O)(OCH₃)₂)]⁻ and **2Ln** complexes where [L²]⁻=[(C₆H₅S(O)₂NP(O)(C₆H₄-*p*-CH₃)₂)]⁻ will be compared with those obtained for the earlier investigated compounds - Na[Ln(L³)₄] where [L³]⁻=[(*p*-CH₃)C₆H₄S(O)₂NP(O)(OCH₃)₂]⁻.

In these ligands, that are P, N, S – hetero-substituted analogs of β-diketones, the number of C=O vibrations (~1600 cm⁻¹), present in β-diketones, have been eliminated. They have been replaced with the low energetic vibrations P=O (~1250 cm⁻¹) and S=O (~1350 cm⁻¹). Replacing of the carbon atom at the same time, which is in β-diketones, with the nitrogen atom eliminates high-power vibrations of C-H from six-membered chelate ring, which is created as a result of coordination with the lanthanide ion. This reduces the multiphonon quenching of lanthanide emission. Photophysical properties in combination with the thermodynamic stability of the complexes, their resistance to UV radiation, and even on synchrotron radiation, create potential possibilities for constructing of light converting molecular devices.

Interaction of Cu(II) ions with human serum amyloid A

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Serum amyloid A (SAA) is a major constituent of secondary amyloidosis diseases resulting from prolonged acute inflammation, for example due to rheumatoid arthritis. N-terminal part of this protein tends to form amyloid fibrils when the structure of the protein is destabilized by proteolytic cleavage. Recent crystallographic structure of SAA revealed that the protein is stabilized by its C-terminal part, forming multiple specific interactions with three out of four core α -helices of SAA [1]. SAA fragment of C-terminal residues 86-104 and its mutants were subject to studies of interactions with copper ions. Coordination of Cu(II) ions by the peptides was characterized with potentiometric and spectroscopic methods.

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SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION AND CATALYTIC ACTIVITIES OF VANADIUM COMPLEXES CONTAINING LINEAR TETRADENTATE LIGANDS.

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Polydentate diaminebis(aryloxydo) (ONNO) ligands have been proved to be the source of versatile ligands for many transition metals including vanadium(III-V)[1]. Particular attention has recently been paid to the synthesis and study of this kind of ligands and their complexes. This is due to their various structural and magnetic features as well as biological models for understanding the structure of biologically active systems, especially vanadium-dependent enzymes[2].

Metal catalyzed oxidations of organic substrates have immense importance from synthetic as well as biochemical point of view. The potential catalytic ability of vanadium compounds has led to an increasing interest in vanadium coordination chemistry. A variety of oxovanadium complexes have been shown to catalyze alkenes by several oxidant, such as hydrogenperoxide (H₂O₂) and tert-butylhydroperoxide (TBHP)[3].

The biological and catalytic relevance of vanadium has prompted the synthesis of numerous model vanadium compounds based on the diaminebis(aryloxydo) ligands, their structural, spectroscopic and magnetic properties will be presented in details.

Scheme 1. Synthetic strategy.

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Copper(I) complexes with phosphine derived from sparfloxacin: structures, spectroscopic properties and cytotoxicity.

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Design and synthesis of new drugs is time-consuming and expensive. Their launch takes at least 10 years, while the cost reaches up to billions of dollars. Despite the large number of available drugs of various properties, we are still struggling with many diseases, adverse drug reaction and drug resistance [1-2]. More and more often in the design of therapeutic substances, a completely different approach is used than the search for new classes of compounds [3]. Namely, it is becoming popular to modify the structures which are used in medical therapeutics by attaching other chemical moieties, responsible for their more-selective transport or for changing the biological properties [4].

Medicinal inorganic chemistry offers additional opportunities for the design of therapeutic agents, not accessible for organic chemistry [5]. The wide range of coordination numbers and geometries, different redox states available, various thermodynamic and kinetic properties, as well as the intrinsic properties of metal ions provide a variety of reactions. It can result in compounds which are very interesting from a medicinal point of view [6].

Fig. 1 Schematic view of the complexes and ligands (with atomic numeration) and synthetic routes.

We present new copper(I) iodide or copper(I) thiocyanate complexes with hydroxymethyldiphenylphosphine (PPh₂(CH₂OH); POH) or phosphine derivative of sparfloxacin (HSf) - a 3rd generation fluoroquinolone antibiotic agent (PPh₂(CH₂-Sf); PSf) and 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline (dmp) or 2,2'-biquinoline (bq) auxiliary ligands (**figure 1**). The synthesized complexes were fully characterized by NMR and UV-Vis spectroscopies as well as mass spectrometry. Selected structures were additionally analyzed by X-ray and DFT methods. All complexes proved to be stable in solution in the presence of water and atmospheric oxygen for several days. Cytotoxic activity of the complexes was tested against two cancer cell lines (CT26 - mouse colon carcinoma and A549 - human lung adenocarcinoma). The studies applying two different incubation times led to preliminary estimation of the dependence of selectivity and mechanism of action on the diimine and phosphine ligands type. Obtained results showed that the complexes with PPh₂(CH₂-Sf) are significantly more active than those with PPh₂(CH₂OH). On the other hand, the relative impact of the diimine on the cytotoxicity is less pronounced. However the dmp complexes are characterized by the strong inhibitory properties, while the bq ones are rather not. It proves the interesting and promising biological properties of the investigated group of copper(I) complexes, which undoubtedly are worth of further biological studies.

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Acid-Base and Complexing Properties Oxalodihydrazide, Acethydrazide and Formic Hydrazide with Cu(II) in Aqueous Solution

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Hydrazides are compounds containing neighbouring strong N and O donor groups. Template synthesis with hydrazides has been widely used as a powerful tool for the creation of functionalised macrocyclic complexes [1]. Some of them as well as their complexes demonstrate *inter alia* antibacterial [2] and anticancer [3] activity. The hydrazide derivatives have revealed a high binding ability towards *d*- and some toxic heavy ions [4].

We begin the investigation of selected hydrazide ligands and their Cu(II) complexes in solution with the aim of obtaining new information about their protolytic and metal-ion coordination abilities. The present work uses three hydrazide ligands of various structures and with varying numbers of donor groups: oxalodihydrazide, (NH₂NHCO)₂; acethydrazide, NH₂NHCOCH₃ and formic hydrazide, NH₂NHCOH. The structural formulas of the ligands are as follows:

oxalodihydrazide

acethydrazide

formic hydrazide

The presence of amine nitrogen atoms makes it possible for ligands to accept and then dissociate protons from acidic solutions within the pH range 2-5: the lowest pH for oxalodihydrazide and the highest for acethydrazide. According to the literature data, the ligands discussed exist in the ketone tautomeric form under these conditions [5]. On the other hand, only the amide groups are capable of dissociation in alkaline medium. These dissociation constants were determined by potentiometric titrations carried out across a wide pH range.

UV-Vis spectra in the presence of copper(II) showed that the complexes are formed below pH 2, which suggests that the carbonyl oxygen is the first accessible copper binding site. In the case of acethydrazide, additional studies with a copper(II) electrode have shown that complexes associated with the participation of amine nitrogens are formed above pH 3.

However, precipitation of the hydrolytic products disturbs the observation of possible complex formation with the N-amide atoms, confirmed up to now only in solid state as an initial step of template synthesis. Further studies of the mentioned Cu(II) – hydrazide systems, in particular EPR spectroscopy, are currently in progress.

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Plasmidic DNA photocleavage of a new arene Ru (II) hydroxy benzyl benzothiazole derivative

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The main challenge in the search for ruthenium-based anticancer drugs is related to their potential targets. With this in mind, two main strategies are currently applied. The first option is the design of complexes with certain ligands that may improve their cellular uptake and therefore their tumour selectivity; the second is the use of nontoxic pro-drugs that require activation within the cancer cells [1]. To this aim, photochemical activation of pro-drugs has been widely applied and several light-activated DNA binding complexes have been developed so far [2].

Photodynamic therapy (PDT) constitutes a new effective type of non-invasive chemotherapeutic treatment that may offer over radiotherapy, surgery or traditional chemotherapy, advantages such as control of time, spatial activation of the photosensitizer and no resistance mechanism. It is based on a nontoxic photosensitizer molecule that can be excited upon irradiation, reaching a triplet excited state by intersystem crossing. Once this state is reached, the molecule can undergo three types of reactions. Type I, is electron transfer to O₂ or other oxygen-containing species in solution, which eventually results in ROS (reactive oxygen species) generation. Type II occurs when the photosensitizer can transfer energy to molecular oxygen, forming highly reactive singlet oxygen (¹O₂). Type III stems from electron transfer from the photosensitizer excited state to cellular targets [3].

This work addresses the synthesis of a new Ru (II) arene photosensitizer with 2-(2'-hydroxybenzyl)-benzothiazole (hphbzTh) as ligand (Figure 1). ¹H-NMR experiments have shown that this complex undergoes photolysis of the arene moiety upon irradiation. No biological activity was expected for the free *p*-cym; nevertheless, the arene released leads to a free position in the metal coordination sphere. There are multiple cellular targets prone to interact with this residue.

The DNA photocleavage activity of this drug was tested both in the dark and upon irradiation, revealing that DNA cleavage occurs only when the complex is pre-irradiated alone or in the

Figure 1. [Ru(NCS)(p-cym)(hphbzTh)].

presence of the plasmid. Therefore, the DNA cleavage is due to photoactivation of the ruthenium complex. The cleavage activity depends on the drug concentration, the irradiation time and on whether the drug was pre-irradiated or not prior to incubation with the plasmid. Thus, for the same metal complex concentration and irradiation time, the photo cleavage activity is noticeably increased when the drug and the plasmid are irradiated together.

To elucidate if the cleavage is related to ROS formation upon drug irradiation, the DNA photo cleavage activity was evaluated in the presence of several ROS scavengers such as DMSO, mannitol, Hys or SOD. Interestingly, the cleavage is significantly inhibited in the presence of SOD, revealing that superoxide radicals are involved in the observed DNA photo cleavage.

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Synthesis, structure and reactivity of iron(II) clathrochelates with terminal formyl groups and their further functionalization for target delivery to biological systems

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Iron(II) mono- and bis-clathrochelates are reported [1–5] to be efficient transcription inhibitors and antifibrillogenic agents due to them forming supramolecular assemblies with biological macromolecules. Therefore, it is important to obtain these mono- and bis-macrobicyclic compounds with desirable reactive substituents that can be used for further functionalization with a fragment designed for target delivery of clathrochelates to a given biological system.

We have obtained 3- and 4-formylphenylboron-capped iron(II) tris-dioximates by direct template condensation of three molecules of the corresponding aliphatic α -dioxime or dichloroglyoxime with 3- and 4-formylboronic acids as Lewis acidic capping (cross-linking) agents on a Fe^{2+} ion as a matrix

Figure

iron(II) clathrochelates with ribbed mercaptobenzoic substituents (Scheme 2).

Scheme 1

(an example is shown in Scheme 1). With methanol as a solvent, these *one-pot* reactions also gave macrobicyclic acetals (Fig.) that were converted to formyl-terminated iron(II) clathrochelates by H^+ -catalysed hydrolysis. These reactive complexes underwent further H^+ -catalysed condensation with isoniazid as a hydrazone component to give hydrazonate cage complexes functionalized for their target delivery to biological systems. Nucleophilic substitution of reactive chlorine atoms of the corresponding hexachlorocyclotriphosphazene precursor with thiolate ions as nucleophiles afforded hexasulfide iron(II) clathrochelates with ribbed mercaptobenzoic substituents (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

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Probing Cu⁺ Binding Properties of Cysteine-Rich Fragment of BRI2 the natural inhibitor of A β aggregation

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The amyloid- β peptide (A β) and its precursor protein (APP) are known to interact with number of protein partners located within or in close proximity to cellular membrane. The evolution of amyloid is related to the activity of secretases.[1] They are involved in posttranslational processing of the 1st type of membrane proteins (e.g. APP). Their activity can be modulated by multiple agents such as BRI2 protein which interacts with the APP, thus shielding the site of proteolytic cleavage.[2] BRI2 is a subject of post-translational proteolytic treatment that yields peptidic fragments of BRI2 both inside and outside the cell.[3] Two of them are particularly interesting; 10kDa domain ICD containing cysteine-rich segment of BRI2 acting as a secondary messenger of cellular signals,[2] and a peptide called BRI2-23 which has a capacity of braking aggregation of A β in vivo and in vitro.[4] APP and A β are involved in the copper ions homeostasis. Since this might be influenced by protein interactome, the evaluation of metal binding properties of cysteine-rich domains of BRI2 and C-terminal furin cleaved peptide (BRI2-23) [5] towards Cu(I) ions or its metallic molecular probes like Hg(II) and Ag(I) is of particular importance. In this work we have used Hg(II) and Ag(I) to probe the interactions of Cu(I) with peptidic model of cysteine-rich domain of BRI2.

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Copper(II) complexes of terminally free alloferon mutants containing two histidyl binding sites inside peptide chain Structure Stability and Biological Activity

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It seems that natural compounds derived from plants, microorganisms, fungi and animal secondary metabolites may have potential use as therapeutic agents. However, as research shows that insects are a group of animals that can produce compounds with antibacterial, antiviral and anticancer properties. Examples of such compounds are alloferons. Alloferon 1 is a linear tridecapeptide with the following amino acid sequences: H-His¹-Gly-Val-Ser-Gly-His⁶-Gly-Gln-His⁹-Gly-Val-His¹²-Gly-OH, while alloferon 2 is composed of 12 amino acids with the following sequence: H-Gly-Val-Ser-Gly-His⁵-Gly-Gln-His⁸-Gly-Val-His¹¹-Gly-OH. These peptides were discovered by Chernysh in 2002 in the blood of the insect *Calliphora vicina* (Diptera) previously infected by bacteria gram-negative *Escherichia coli* and gram positive *Micrococcus luteus* [1,2]. *In vivo* experiments reveal that alloferon induces interferon (IFN) synthesis in mice [1].

Mononuclear and polynuclear copper(II) complexes of the alloferon 1 with point mutations H1A/H12A A¹GVSH⁶GQH⁹GVA¹²G-COOH, H1A/H9A A¹GVSH⁶GQA⁹GVH¹²G-COOH, and H1A/H6A A¹GVSA⁶GQH⁹GVH¹²G-COOH have been studied by potentiometric, UV-visible, CD, and EPR spectroscopic, and mass spectrometry (MS) methods. Complete complex speciation at different metal-to-ligand ratios ranging from 1:1 to 3:1 was obtained. In wide 6-8 pH range, including physiological pH 7.4, and a 1:1 metal-to-ligand molar ratio, the peptides studied form the CuH₁L complex with the {NH₂,N⁻,2N_{Im}} coordination mode. The presence of the 4N binding site for the CuH₁L complexes prevents the deprotonation and coordination of the second amide nitrogen atom to copper(II) ions (pK_{1/2} 7.83 – 8.07) in comparison to that of pentaGly (6.81).

The induction of apoptosis and phenoloxidase activity *in vivo* in *T. molitor* by the ligands and their Cu(II) complexes were studied. The biological results induction of apoptosis show that the Cu(II)-H1A/H9A system is the most active while the H1A/H9A peptide is inactive.

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Selectivity of nitroimidazole-ruthenium polypyridyl ruthenium conjugate towards cancer cells under hypoxic conditions

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Ruthenium polypyridyl complexes have been initially studied as structure- and site-specific DNA probes and nucleus imaging agents in biological systems [1, 2]. Despite high DNA binding constant ($> 10^6 \text{ M}^{-1}$) [3], ruthenium complexes demonstrate excellent cellular internalization with rather limited nuclear accumulation in live cells [4]. Ruthenium polypyridyl complexes possess unique optical features (intense and long lifetime luminescence strongly depending on the molecular oxygen concentration, emission close to near-infrared) and interesting biological properties (ability to pass cellular membrane, reasonable solubility in aqueous media, toxicity against cancer cell lines). Therefore during the last decade a growing interest in applications of Ru polypyridyl complexes as luminescent dyes for optical imaging or as cytotoxic agents for the treatment of various types of cancer has been observed [2, 5-8].

2-Nitroimidazoles are the group of bioreductive prodrugs which are developed toward their application in diagnosis and therapy of hypoxic tissues often typical for solid tumors [9]. Pimonidazole has been commonly applied for the detection and quantification of hypoxia [9] and currently is studied as an invasive hypoxia diagnostic tool for pancreatic tumor in a pre-operation treatment [10]. 2-nitroimidazole moiety was attached to the ruthenium polypyridyl core (see Scheme) to create a unit with potential therapeutic (cytotoxic) features as well as ability to imaging hypoxic tissues by noninvasive techniques (fluorescence molecular tomography (FMT) or fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM)) [11, 12].

To study the selectivity of new Ru conjugate on cells under hypoxic conditions numerous experiments were designed. The cytotoxicity of $[\text{Ru}(\text{dip})_2(\text{bpy-NitroIm})]\text{Cl}_2$ on

several cell lines under normoxic and hypoxic conditions was evaluated using Alamar Blue test. Ru compound was found to be slightly more cytotoxic under hypoxic conditions. Cellular uptake of Ru complex under low oxygen concentration was monitored directly by following the luminescent signal of treated cells using flow cytometry. Accumulation study was carried out in medium with or without serum for different incubation time on several cell lines (A549, MLuMEC FVB, 4T1). Presence of hypoxia-induced nitroreductase appeared to be essential for the higher uptake of $[\text{Ru}(\text{dip})_2(\text{bpy-NitroIm})]\text{Cl}_2$ under hypoxic conditions.

To confirm the ability of new synthesized ruthenium complex to be “trapped” inside the cells under hypoxic conditions, the intensity of luminescence of treated cells was measured after one day of growth in Ru-free medium. Ru-nitroimidazole conjugate preserved its luminescence up to 83–89% and this level is ca. 30% higher than found for parental complex $[\text{Ru}(\text{dip})_2(\text{bpy})]\text{Cl}_2$. Results suggest that $[\text{Ru}(\text{dip})_2(\text{bpy-NitroIm})]\text{Cl}_2$ can be trapped inside the cells due to reduction of nitro group follow by its binding to biomolecules under hypoxic conditions.

The reduction of nitroimidazole moiety of Ru conjugate under hypoxic conditions reaction by nitroreductase was confirmed using fluorescence and IR spectroscopy. Several products of such reduction were identified by mass spectroscopy.

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Polynuclear complexes based on Cu(II) and aminopolycarboxylic acids: Synthesis, solution chemistry and crystal structures

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The design and preparation of novel polynuclear coordination compounds (and in particular coordination polymers) is a subject of current interest due to their promising applications in gas storage, catalysis, drug delivery, magnetochemistry or supramolecular chemistry.[1] Most of the work reported up to now is based on the use of rigid, highly directional ligands to connect metal ions, a route of choice if specific crystal motifs are wanted.[2] Recently, however, the use of flexible ligands has caught the attention of several groups because this property is essential in the design of novel molecular devices whose functionality is based on conformational changes.[3] The breathing ability of certain solid-state polymers is a good example of this.[4]

In this work we report the preparation of novel polynuclear complexes using flexible aminopolycarboxylic acid ligands H₂mdp, H₂bdp and H₃cfida (Fig. 1) to connect Cu(II) ions. The syntheses were carried out in aqueous acidic solution (pH values between 3 and 5) to attain the protonation of the nitrogen atom and avoid the interaction of this atom with the metal ions. This fact facilitated the polytopic capability of the polycarboxylates resulting in different architectures (dinuclear complexes or polymeric structures).

Figure 1 – Structure of aminopolycarboxylic acid used in this work.

In order to choose the appropriate reaction conditions, the behaviour of the ligands and the ligand-metal systems in aqueous solution was studied by high resolution potentiometry. Stability constants were measured at 20 °C and 0.5 M NMe₄Cl and protonation constants for bdp²⁻ together with formation constants for the complexes with a series of metal ions (Mn²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺) are reported. The formation of polynuclear coordination compounds with the different ligands is discussed, in terms of the nature of the starting

materials and the reaction conditions. The compounds were characterized at the solid state by IR spectroscopy, elemental analysis and single crystal X-ray diffraction.

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Effect of alkali metal ions on dissociation kinetics of Cu(II) complexes of DOTP-like macrocyclic ligands

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Tetraaza-macrocyclic ligands based on cyclen skeleton are well known for their great ability to bind copper(II) ion leading to formation of metal complexes of high thermodynamic stability and kinetic inertness which are required for their *in vivo* applications and in medicine [1–3]. Some complexes of copper radioisotopes are utilized in diagnosis (positron emission tomography - PET, ⁶⁴Cu with half-life 12.8 h) or in radio-immunotherapy (⁶⁷Cu with half-life 62 h) [4]. In addition, the sodium and potassium ions play an important role in biology, e.g. concentration gradient of sodium/potassium ions is important in living organism for many cell functions, and their presence in the solution can affect the kinetic inertness of copper(II) complexes.

Scheme. Formulas of macrocyclic ligands in the studied copper(II) complexes.

In this work, the acid-assisted dissociation kinetics of Cu(II) complexes with DOTP-like ligands (e.g. H₆do3p, H₆do3p1ol, H₈dotp [1, 2]; Scheme) was studied by means of molecular absorption spectroscopy in presence of Li⁺, Na⁺ and K⁺ salts employed as supporting electrolyte. It was found out that these ions significantly influence the rate of dissociation of copper(II) complex in K⁺ < Na⁺ < Li⁺ order and the parameters of chemical model describing this reaction correlate with their ionic size [5, 6]. This effect was not observed for analogous H₄dota ligand. This phenomenon is important for interpretation of reaction mechanism of

copper(II) complex dissociation and it can be explained by formation of weak complexes between the phosphonate group and the alkali metal ions, analogously as described for lanthanide(III) complexes of DOTP [6].

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Copper(II)-(N-Allyliminodiacetate) Chelates with and without Selected N-heterocyclic Ligands

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N-alkyne- [1,2] and N-alkene-iminodiacetic acids [3] have recently gained a broad interest in the preparation of useful materials for a variety of technical applications. These chelating agents were synthesized and studied in solution long time ago. The N-allyliminodiacetic acid (H₂alida) was studied as a ligand in solution for Ag(I) and M(II) ions (M = Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, and Cd) by L. Pettit et al. [4]. Now we report the synthesis and crystal structure of the binary ‘acid’ bis-chelate (**1**) as well as three mixed-ligand Cu(II) complexes having imidazole (Him, **2**), 2,4-diaminopyrimidine (2,4-dapyd, **3**) and 7-azaindole (H7azain, **4**) as simplified moieties of purine ligands (**2**, **3**, **4**).

The crystal of compound **1** [Cu(Halida)₂]₂·2H₂O (monoclinic, *P*2₁/*c*, 100 K, final *R*₁ 0.034) consists of centro-symmetric complex molecules and non-coordinated water. The complex exhibits an elongated octahedral coordination, type 4+2. The Halida⁻ chelator displays a *fac*-NO+O(carboxylic) conformation. The trans-apical/distal coordination sites are occupied by the non-protonated carboxylic O-donor atoms (Cu-O 2.603(1) Å). The formation of this species was not observed in solution [4].

Compound **2** [Cu(μ₂-alida)(Him)]_n (monoclinic, *P*2₁/*n*, 100 K, final *R*₁ 0.041) crystallizes as a 1-D polymer. Here, Him represents the five-membered ring fragment of any purine ligand. In the crystal complex chains extend parallel to the *b* axis, which are further

connected by symmetry related inter-molecular interactions in a 2D-framework: (Him)N-H \cdots O(alida) (2.742(4) Å and 172.6°) and Him-Him π,π -stacking (inter-centroid distance 3.43 Å).

Compound **3** [Cu(alida)(2,4-dapyd)(H₂O)] (monoclinic, $P2_1/c$, 100 K, final R_1 0.048) and **4** [Cu(alida)(H7azain)(H₂O)] (monoclinic, $P2_1/c$, 100 K, final R_1 0.030) display similar structures built by molecular H-bonded 3D-frameworks (see figure below). 2,4-dapyd resembles the six-membered ring of 2,6-diaminopurine while H7azain is a 1,6,7-trideazaadenine. In **3**, the less-hindered Cu-N3 bond (1.996(3) Å) cooperates with the intra-molecular interligand interaction N22-H22A \cdots O4(alida) (2.793(4) Å, 140.9°). In **4**, H7azain exhibits its most stable tautomer (H(N9)7azain). Thus, H7azain shows the Cu1-N23 coordination bond (1.982(2) Å) cooperating with the intra-molecular interligand interaction N29-H29 \cdots O8(alida) (2.789(2) Å, 125.1°). In these mixed-ligand complexes the alida chelator exhibits a fac-NO+O(carboxylate) conformation.

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Copper(II) complexes with vitamin B₆ as potential antimicrobial agents

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Metal ions play key roles in the structural organization and activation of certain enzymes, which are involved in the transfer of genetic information from DNA. Metal ions commonly used form low molecular weight complexes and therefore, prove to be active against several diseases.

Biologically relevant metal complexes have several requirements in terms of their structure. First, a biologically active metal complex should have a sufficiently high thermodynamic stability to deliver the metal to the active site. The metal-ligand binding should be hydrolytically stable. The compounds of low molecular weight with neutral charge and some water solubility are soluble in almost any medium and may permeate through biological membranes by passive diffusion [1].

The present investigations showed the detailed study with regard to the mode of binding of pyridoxamine(pm), pyridoxine(pn) and pyridoxal (**Figure 1**) with Cu(II) ion in solution, using two independent methods (spectroscopy UV-Vis and potentiometry).

Figure 1. The natural forms of vitamin B₆: a) pyridoxamine (*pm*), b) pyridoxal (*pl*), c) pyridoxine (*pn*).

The stability constants (gradual and cumulative) have been determined by using EQUID and CVEQUID computer programs. Copper(II) ion forms the most stable coordination compounds with pyridoxamine (*pm*), while the weakest one with pyridoxal (*pl*).

The six-coordinated complexes of Cu(II) incorporating pyridoxamine and pyridoxine ligands were synthesized and characterized in details by means of spectroscopy (FT-IR, UV-Vis), elemental analysis and conductivity measurements. The obtained results have shown that the complex of vitamin B₆ with nitrate salt of copper(II) is six-coordinated formed by two N,O-bonded chelate pyridoxamine ligands and one bidentate nitrate ion, while six-coordination of pyridoxine complex is formed *via* two O,O-bonded *pn* ligands and one bidentate nitrate ion.

The ligands and their complexes have been screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activity against Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria and yeast. The biological activity data present that the Cu(II) complexes are more potent antimicrobials than the parent ligands. The results of biological assay show that [Cu(O₂NO)(pm)₂]NO₃ has higher activity against tested microorganism strains than the [Cu(O₂NO)(pn)₂]NO₃ [2,3].

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Distribution of metals in temperate beachrocks

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The Nerbioi-Ibaizabal estuary (northeastern Spain) is an area highly influenced by the industrialization developed since the second half of the 19th century. Although the resulting deficient environmental quality of the system has been considerably improved nowadays, many of the beaches placed eastwards to the estuary might require special attention; especially those affected by a phenomenon known as *beachrock*, which consists on coastal sedimentary structures formed in the intertidal zone through an early precipitation of carbonates. The driving forces of the cementation are still a matter of debate, however, physicochemical and/or biological processes are believed to be involved in the process. It is a common phenomenon in tropical and subtropical coasts, but not that much in the analysed temperate latitudes [1]. Apart from that, in the case study, it is remarkable the high presence of slag and anthropogenic materials within the cemented matrix. To understand this situation, impacts like a wide variety of anthropogenic wastes inputs coming from the river and the presence of a blast furnace slag disposal zone must be taken into account.

This work is focused on the metal distribution of different beachrock outcrops, in an attempt to get a general overview of the metal content trapped in there, and later on examine the possible release of the contaminants to the system due to the erosion agents to which the structures might be exposed. For that purpose, two beaches were examined. One of them, Arrigunaga, is placed in the mouth of the estuary and in spite of the mechanical removal of cemented sand during a regeneration process conducted fifteen years ago, nowadays cemented structures are still visible. In contrast, the second location, La Salvaje, is an open beach and the outermost eastward location where the cementation has been found so far. Samples were gathered from one side to another in the longitudinal sense of the beaches, but also transversally at different tidal levels. Afterwards, the analyses were carried out through a microwave assisted HNO₃-HCl extraction, followed by ICP-MS determinations complemented with chemometric analyses.

In general terms, Ca, Al, Mg, Fe, Mn, Na, and K were the major elements found in all the samples. Regarding Arrigunaga beach, the longitudinal trend showed that the concentration of those major elements increases northward. Although they could come from the surrounding geological characteristics, the estuary system is generally enriched in Fe and Mn due to the industrialization activities suffered along the years [2]. Furthermore, previous to the regeneration of the beach, the marine dynamics apparently favoured the transport of sediments to the mentioned northernmost point, possibly explaining their higher accumulation

at that point. In any case, it cannot be discarded either the fairly constant concentration of minor elements like Ti, Ba, Zn, Cu, V, Cr, Ni and As among others, in the north-south direction of the beach, likely to come from external anthropogenic inputs also. In La Salvaje, in contrast, most of the major elements have a constant concentration from side to side of the beach. But, the further the outcrop is located from the estuary, the lesser seems to be the amount of most of the aforementioned minor contaminants. The sediment transport from the estuary is generally influenced by eastward prevailing flow, so the distribution of the minor elements in La Salvaje might show that the possible enrichment of those elements is prone to decrease in that direction. These dissimilarities in the distribution of major and minor elements in both settings might denote that each beach was differently affected by the various nearby human impacts.

Regarding the samples at different tidal levels, the difference between the distribution of major and minor elements is not that marked. In Arrigunaga Ca, but also elements like Pb, Cr and V show a seaward higher concentration trend, while most of the rest of the elements are quite constant. In any case, it can be challenging to set a tendency in Arrigunaga, because as the outcrops were possibly mostly removed at those points during the regeneration of the beach, the ones that are visible nowadays might not thoroughly represent the path of the external input of metals. On the contrary, examining the samples at different tidal levels in La Salvaje, many of the major and minor elements seem to be present in higher concentration in those samples closer to the seawater, probably illustrating more clearly the source of the contaminants.

This first estimation of the metal content might help to understand the context in which the beachrock was formed. For example, the metal input is an indicator of the sediments supply provided to the beach for beachrock formation. Moreover, the metal complexes and other composites, such as, organic matter might have eased the retention of the contaminants into the cemented structures, reflecting the human pressure on the area.

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Factors Affecting the Design of Biomimetic Ferrichrome Analogues

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Iron is an essential element for virtually all life forms. However, in the oxidizing earth atmosphere it exists as insoluble ferric (Fe(III)) polymers. To overcome iron deficiency, microorganisms have developed a unique acquisition system. This system consists of: (i) secreted iron chelators, called siderophores, which bind and solubilize iron, and (ii) specific outer membrane receptors, that deliver the siderophore-iron complex into the microbial cell by active transport.

The Biomimetic Chemistry approach, followed in our laboratory, aims at reproducing or mimicking the functions of natural products rather than their detailed structure. A library of new biomimetic ferrichrome analogues was prepared. The cyclic hexapeptide of the natural ferrichrome was replaced by symmetric tripodal triamine or alternatively triacid template. The template was extended with arms constructed from amino acids and other similar derivatives that could provide suitable arm spacers, all analogues were terminated by a hydroxamate chelating units. Both structural and stereo-isomers (L-AA and D-AA enantiomers) have been prepared. The new analogues differ in their length and the location of the external residues, with respect to the coordinated metal binding site.

The physiochemical properties of the new analogues, together with their biological potency and growth preferences in two Gram negative bacterial strains, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas putida*, will be presented and discussed. While some analogues are species-specific to *P. putida*, others present broad-range activity, targeting both *P. putida* and *E. coli* (similarly to native ferrichrome). The differences in Fe (III) uptake in these two model bacteria can provide guidelines required for structural optimization leading to broad-range activity. Minor modifications of the optimized structure may induce formation of species-specific analogues utilizing practically the same platform. While species-specificity offers the potential to develop fast selective diagnostic tools, broad-range activity may have therapeutic advantages, as siderophores have no mammalian targets and are therefore nontoxic. Siderophore drug-conjugates might hold the promise of novel antimicrobial agents.

Solution study of the interactions of copper(II) ions with thiosemicarbazones

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Thiosemicarbazones (TSCs) are a class of compounds with a very wide range of applications, e.g., spectrophotometric and spectrofluorimetric detection of various metal ions. The ability of TSCs to form stable complexes with important biological metal ions makes them also versatile pharmacophores. They possess a broad range of pharmaceutical properties such as antimalarial, antimicrobial and antitumor activity [1, 2].

Taking into account the fact that cancer is one of the main health concerns confronting humanity and one of the primary targets in therapeutic chemistry, studies of new compounds which may possess antitumor properties are very important [3]. Triapine (Figure 1) is the best known example of TSCs family and has been extensively studied as a single agent and in combination with established drugs in phase I and phase II clinical trials with mixed results [4].

Figure 1: Structure of Triapine.

In connection with the anticancer applications of TSCs there have been proposed several mechanisms of action, but many questions still remain unanswered. Information on the speciation of metal complexes, particularly at physiological pH, can be the first step towards elucidation of the cytotoxic mechanism of TSCs. In this work, we characterize novel thiosemicarbazone ligands, in terms of complex formation with Cu(II) ions and their stability constants.

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Influence of N-heterocyclic ligands in NAMI-A-type complexes on interaction with NO and angiogenesis process in endothelial cells

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NAMI-A, [ImH][RuCl₄(Im)(DMSO)], is a most promising antitumor agent due to its selective inhibiting properties of metastasis formation and growth and its negligible cytotoxic effect [1]. One of the concepts explaining the antimetastatic activity of NAMI-A assumes its interference in NO-related angiogenesis processes *in vivo* [2]. Furthermore, the *in vivo* studies revealed the significant role of coordinated dimethylsulfoxide on antimetastatic activity of NAMI-A [3, 4]. The strength of DMSO coordination is markedly influenced by the nature of heterocyclic nitrogen ligand coordinated to ruthenium in *trans* position to DMSO [5]. *In vitro* and *in vivo* studies on series of complexes, similar in structure to NAMI-A have shown that the nature of heterocyclic nitrogen ligand influences the reduction of metastases in mammary carcinoma [6]. Moreover, the nature of the N-heterocyclic ligand coordinated to the ruthenium has been shown to play a role in cell distribution along the cell cycle phases, since RuCl₄(DMSO)(N-ligand) with pyrazole, thiazole and pyrazine do not arrest the cell cycle in G₂-M phase as opposed to imidazole substituted species (NAMI-A) [6].

The aim of the presented studies was to check the influence of the nature of the N-heterocyclic ligands in NAMI-A-type complexes on their interaction with NO and redox properties of ruthenium nitrosyl derivatives of general formula ([Ru^{II}Cl₃(N-ligand)(DMSO)(NO⁺))] as well as on pseudo-vessel formation by human skin microvascular endothelial cells (HSkMEC). Our previous studies revealed that NAMI-A complex may interfere in NO metabolism by coordinating NO under physiological conditions; however NAMI-A nitrosyl derivatives due to a relatively high negative reduction potential are not able to release NO via one electron reduction [7].

In this context we synthesized NAMI-A-type complexes with indazole (IND), [Ru^{III}Cl₄(IND)(DMSO)]⁻, and isoquinoline (ISQ), [Ru^{III}Cl₄(ISQ)(DMSO)]⁻, ligands in the *trans* position to DMSO. The influence of N-heterocyclic ligand on the reactivity of ruthenium complexes with NO was studied with the application of spectrophotometric and electrochemical methods under physiological-like conditions. Angiogenesis was evaluated by the formation of pseudo-vessels on Matrigel under normoxic and hypoxic conditions. The decrease in pseudo-vessels mean-length and their number was observed for cells treated with [Ru^{III}Cl₄(IND)(DMSO)]⁻, and [Ru^{III}Cl₄(ISQ)(DMSO)]⁻ under hypoxic conditions (Figure 1), whereas NAMI-A complex did not inhibit angiogenesis.

Figure 1. Effect of $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}\text{Cl}_4(\text{IND})(\text{DMSO})]^-$ on angiogenesis by skin endothelial cells (HskMEC) under hypoxic conditions.

The influence of the studied compounds on cell migration was studied by the scratch method under normoxic and hypoxic conditions. Moreover, the effect of studied compounds on selected gene expression, related with angiogenesis process, will be reported.

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A potentiometric, spectrophotometric and NMR study of protonation and formation equilibria of four new iron chelators.

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The use of chelating agents for iron overload diseases has found ever increasing attention [1-2]. The different drawbacks presented by the chelating agents nowadays in use ask for research on new chelating drugs.

In the frame of our research on Fe^{III} and Al^{III} chelators, a number of ligands containing two kojic acid units joined by different linkers were designed, synthesized, characterized by solid state X-ray diffraction and quantum chemical calculation, and their protonation and Fe^{III} and Al^{III} complex formation equilibria, using a variety of techniques such as potentiometry, spectrophotometry, ESI-MS, NMR, were exhaustively studied [3-7].

The ligands bearing in the linker a vanillin/ortho-vanillin residue were found promising as iron chelators. Here we will present four similar molecules in which the vanillin/ortho-vanillin residue has been substituted by an aromatic ring containing a carboxylic or a phenolic substituent. Being a phenolic group characterized by a pK ~ 9 and a carboxylic by a pK ~ 4, this substitution was intended to evaluate how the protonation constant affects the pMe value.

The topic of this poster will be the study of protonation and metal complex formation equilibria by potentiometric, spectrophotometric and NMR methods.

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The coordination chemistry of ZIP proteins metal complexes

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ZIP proteins are those responsible for divalent metal ions transport across the cell membrane in variety of organisms. We studied the interactions of different ZIP proteins fragments with transition metals and carefully described thermodynamic properties of formed complexes in solution using potentiometry, 2D NMR, mass spectrometry, and CD/UV-vis spectroscopy.

Evolutionarily conserved N-terminal domain of ZIP13 was investigated with Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Bi^{3+} ions [1]. This multi-Cys sequence is interesting mainly from the chemical point of view. Such ligands can be coordinated differently depending on the vicinal amino acids environment and similar sequences are found in e.g. metallothioneins and bacterial chaperones, therefore they are of great interest. The stability of the metal ions complexes of ZIP13 N-terminus decreases in the series $Bi^{3+} \gg Cd^{2+} > Zn^{2+} > Ni^{2+}$.

Stabilities of ZIP13- Zn^{2+} complexes were used as a reference for stability of a fragment of IRT1 protein (ZIP family) [2]. The extracellular loop (between the II and III transmembrane domains) of IRT1 from *Arabidopsis thaliana*, is interesting because of the finding on the behaviour of a whole protein when some particular amino acids from this loop are missing - this unstructured fragment is supposed to be responsible for metal selectivity [3]. An interesting coordination was observed for the IRT1- Zn^{2+} complex, in which two imidazoles (His-96 and His-116), a cysteine thiolate (Cys-109) and one of a carboxyl group of glutamic acid are involved.

Most recently, we have been investigating multi-His metal binding loop between transmembrane domains III and IV of TjZNT1 yeast protein. Metal complexes with Zn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , and additionally Cu^{2+} revealed differences in stability and coordination modes. Surprisingly, Zn^{2+} complexes are more stable than Ni^{2+} [4].

Fig. 1. Graphical representation of ZIP protein. The interaction of (1) N-term of ZIP13, (2) loop between II and III transmembrane domain of IRT1 and (3) loop between III and IV transmembrane domain of TjZNT1 with different transition metals were investigated.

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Zinc, amylin and *C. albicans* zincophores – a possible tug-of-war

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What is the link between amylin (a peptide hormone produced by pancreatic beta cells that regulates glycemic control, being a synergistic partner to insulin [1]) and zincophores from *Candida albicans* (secreted proteins, which specifically bind Zn^{2+} , which can uptake this metal from the environment and re-associate with the fungus via a co-expressed, genetically-linked membrane transporter [2])? The link is not obviously clear, and only latest studies show that amylin (similar to other amyloid-forming proteins) has antimicrobial activity and inhibits the growth of *C. albicans* [3]. Both polypeptides bind zinc ions – zincophores scavenge Zn^{2+} from the host and deliver it to *C. albicans*, and the binding of Zn^{2+} to amylin results in the alteration of the structure of the polypeptide, often leading to the formation of amyloid-like structures. The exact mechanism in which Zn^{2+} affects amylin aggregation is not fully elucidated [4].

In order to check the theory if amylin can compete with zincophores in the binding of Zn^{2+} , a series of thermodynamic and structural analysis of zinc complexes with fragments of amylin and the Pra1 zincophore was performed. Preliminary data suggests that amylin and zincophores might compete for the binding of Zn^{2+} , and that this phenomenon can be one of the molecular basis of the antimicrobial activity of amylin.

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The impact of Cu²⁺ ions on the colistin structure and the nucleic acids degradation properties

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Colistin (polymyxin E) is a cyclic lipodecapeptide. This antibiotic is effective primarily against gram-negative bacteria, in particular, against those strains that are resistant to aminoglycosides, β -lactams and fluorochinolones [1]. Its target is the bacterial outer membrane where the antibiotic's amino groups bind to the acidic lipopolysaccharide molecules by displacing calcium and magnesium. This leads to permeability changes in the cell envelope, leakage of cell contents and finally to cell death [2, 3]. The intravenous formulations of colistin sulphate were gradually abandoned in most parts of the world in the early 1980s because of the reported high incidence of neuro- and nephrotoxicity. In veterinary medicine, colistin is still widely used in the treatment or prevention of infections caused mainly by *Escherichia coli* [4]. Colistin and transition metal ions are commonly used as feed additives for livestock animals [5, 6].

Figure. Structural model of Cu²⁺-colistin complex in water solution at physiological pH (green: copper; blue: nitrogen; red: oxygen; light blue: carbon; white: hydrogen).

The results of an analysis of combined potentiometric and spectroscopic (UV-visible, EPR, CD, NMR) data lead to the conclusion that colistin is able to effectively chelate copper(II) ions. The oxidative activity of the complex manifests itself in the plasmid DNA destruction with simultaneous generation of reactive $\cdot\text{OH}$ species, when accompanied by hydrogen peroxide or ascorbic acid. The way of RNA destruction by ligand alone occurs *via* hydrolytic mechanism. The process of nucleic acid degradation and complex formation may have a potential influence on both animal and human health.

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To mislead the bacteria: the physicochemical analysis of artificial siderophores

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Iron is an essential element for all living organisms. It is involved in many vital metabolic processes. But iron (III) ions in neutral pH are not well soluble, they form precipitation consisting of hydroxide-oxyhydroxide complexes. Therefore, to bind Fe(III) ions bacteria and fungi have evolved the ability to secrete small molecules called siderophores, along with receptors able to recognize and transport Fe(III)-siderophore complexes.

Siderophores are low-weight molecules with high affinity in binding Fe(III) ions. The iron-siderophore complex is recognized by specific receptor, transported into the cell and metal ion is released from an intracellular complex. Due to the ability of some microorganisms to recognize iron complexes with siderophores secreted by other species it is very interesting to determine the factors affecting the process of recognition. Additionally, investigation of mechanisms of iron uptake may provide to novel paths of antibiotic action through “Trojan horse” strategy.

In our research, analogues of ferrichrome, one of hydroxamic siderophores, were investigated. Hexapeptide ring, difficult in synthesis, was replaced by three longer arms, [1], which consist of amino acid (Xaa) and are terminated by retro-hydroxamic group (Figure1).

Figure 1. General structure of ferrichrome analogs; A is the apical site, to which antibiotic or fluorescent molecule might be bound.

Through simplified structure, coordination properties may be modified by elongation of arms or location of additional groups nearby the binding ones. Determination of coordination properties of artificial siderophores with Fe(III) is the key step to understanding the relationship between structure and function of siderophores.

In the physicochemical studies we focused on formation and stability of iron complexes, formed by ligands with different arms' length and with methyl, amino or carboxylic groups nearby the hydroxamic groups.

The binding properties of biomimetic compounds are similar to those of natural ferrichrome. Also, in bacterial growth promotion studies some of the analogues were able to transport iron ions into the bacterial cells. We determined the elements of the structure responsible for Fe(III)-analogue broad or narrow recognition, complex stability and intramolecular interactions.

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Equilibrium and Solution Structural Study of a Cys Containing Oligopeptide Aiming for the Analytical Detection of Toxic Metal Ions

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The improvement of methods for the detection and removal of toxic metal ions and metalloids is one of the most highlighted subjects of environmental chemical research. In addition to their natural abundance, these contaminants also have some anthropogenic sources. If entering the human body, they induce several acute and chronic harmful effects, and thus their rapid, dynamic detection, and detoxification is essential. The application of chemosensors comprising a biomolecule as an effective and selective metal ion binding receptor may be simple alternatives for the sensing of toxic metal ions, besides the current robust instrumental methods. Based on the soft CXXC motif found in numerous transporter [1], storage [2] and chaperon [1] proteins, we designed a short hexapeptide with a sequence of Ac-DCSSCY-NH₂ (DY). Besides the two metal coordinating Cys units we introduced the fluorophore Tyr residue for a potential, fluorescence based signalling of metal ion binding.

Our research objective was to study the interaction of the DY peptide in aqueous solution with mercury(II), cadmium(II) and arsenous acid by means of pH-potentiometry, spectrophotometry, fluorimetry and ¹H-NMR spectroscopy.

In the Hg(II)-containing solutions highly stable species with a composition of Hg(II):DY = 1:1 are formed under strongly acidic conditions. Based on our fluorimetric experiments metal ion binding results in a metal-to-ligand ratio dependent decrease of fluorescence intensity up to a c_{Hg(II)}/c_{DY} = 1:1 composition in the pH = 2 - 6 range. This effect may enable the system to be a candidate for the sensing of Hg(II) ions.

Significant interaction with Cd(II) was found only above pH = 4.5. The quenching of fluorescence by the increase of the metal-to-ligand ratio follows a non-linear trend. In the presence of two-fold ligand excess, the curve shows a clear breakpoint confirming the existence of both mono- and bis-complexes.

Arsenous acid was also observed to coordinate DY, nevertheless, the binding of H₃AsO₃ in the equimolar system at pH = 7.0 is not completed even at a concentration of c_{DY} = 1mM. The rate of complex formation is moderately low in acidic solutions.

In order to test the applicability of the ligand as a potential receptor, we synthesized DY on a solid support, too. Characterization of the immobilized system is in progress.

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Effect of Histidine Localization in a Three Dimensional Branched Peptide on the Cu^{II} Binding properties - Complementary Potentiometric, Spectroscopic and Extended Electrochemical Studies

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Modification of linear and cyclic peptides in order to understand metal binding properties is a popular subject of study due to its high relevance to biology and also application in pharmacy and technology. Peptide branching is an innovative way to influence the metal binding properties of the individual linear fragments.[1] Unique, three dimensional (3D) structures built by multiple peptide chains can also improve some antibacterial [2] and therapeutic[3] agents and also, the metal binding efficiency.[1,4] Unfortunately, the linear and cyclic structures offer only very limited ability for the 3D localization of metal binding donor groups.

Branching of peptides potentially open new perspectives for the copper binding and future application of such complexes. Our previous study demonstrated that branching with the L-2,3-diaminopropionic acid (Dap) is an innovative conception to promote the Cu^{II} binding.[1] The 3D, quasi-tripodal structure of the new series of ligands, H-Gly(H-Gly)DapGly-NH₂ (3G), H-Gly(H-Gly)His-NH₂ (2GH) H-His(H-His)DapGly-NH₂ (2HG) and H-His(H-His)DapHis-NH₂ (3H) offer novel complex geometry and higher effectivity in Cu binding.

An unique strategy has been applied for the characterization of 3H. This method focuses on the role of the 3D individual structural domains in Cu^{II} binding by comparison of 3H either with analogous tetrapeptides involving varying numbers of His and Gly residues.

Potentiometric, spectroscopic (UV-Vis, CD and EPR), mass spectrometric and electrochemical data indicate that in monomeric Cu^{II}-3H complexes the metal is bound with higher affinity at higher range of pH if compared to its structural domains indicating that the effect of 3D branching should be critical factor for future development of novel Cu^{II}-peptide constructs. Upon reduction of Cu^{II} to Cu^I bound in 3H no metal deposition was observed at the electrode, indicating that the ligand can also retain Cu^I from dissociation. Moreover, even the Cu^{III} oxidation state was available in a quasi-reversible electrode process that can be useful in prospective catalytic applications.

This experience can be applied in the design of Cu^{II}-peptide based pharmaceuticals, metal sensors, peptide based Cu^{II} fluoroprobes and also applied in the catalytic/electrocatalytic [5] multi histidine metallopeptides or artificial proteins or enzymes.

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²⁰⁷Pb NMR Studies of Multidentate Oxa-aza Ligand Complexes

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A variety of Pb(II)-complexes, PbL, were studied in water using ²⁰⁷Pb-, ¹H-, ¹³C-, and ³¹P-NMR spectroscopy. The types of ligands studied included EDTA and analogs, EDDADA, EDTAM, TKHPED, TKHED, TPEN, MeEDTA, PDTA, CDTA, CIPhDTA, DTPA, EGTA, BAPTA. Also included were the tetraaza pendent-arm macrocycles DOTA, DOTAM, DOTAEt, DOTKMPA, TETAM, and cryptands 2.2.1, 3.1.1, 2.2.2, 2_N.2_N.2_N. The δ-²⁰⁷Pb values ranged from 1654 to 2618 ppm for EDTA type ligands, from 1109 to 2258 ppm for DOTA and its analogs, and from -64 to 1195 ppm for the cryptands. Linear relationships were observed between the complex formation constant, K_{PbL}, and δ-²⁰⁷Pb for three groups of ligands; 6 coordinate EDTA analogs, 8-coordinate ligands (DOTA analogs, EGTA, BAPTA), and cryptates (2.2.1, 3.1.1, 2.2.2, 2_N.2_N.2_N). Two-dimensional ²⁰⁷Pb-¹H HMQC studies [1] revealed donor atoms (O, N) involved in coordination with the Pb²⁺ center. The pH dependence [2] of δ-²⁰⁷Pb of the complexes Pb(2.2.2)²⁺ and Pb(DOTA)²⁻ is correlated to the formation of species such as Pb(2.2.2)OH⁺ [3] and Pb(HDOTA)⁻ [4].

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Interaction of phytate with biogenic and synthetic polyamines: chemical and structural features of the molecular recognition

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myo-inositol phosphates (InsPs) are a wide variety of ubiquitous molecules with different phosphorylation patterns over the inositol ring [1]. The most abundant InsP is the phytate (InsP₆, Figure 1a), whose biological roles are still not completely understood. The high charge displayed by InsP₆ species under physiological conditions (-8) implies that strong electrostatic interactions should occur with biological cations. During the last years, a great effort has been done to describe the chemical behaviour of InsP₆ in the presence of the most relevant biological metal ions [2]. To complete the chemical speciation of this biomolecule in biological media, we must take into account other physiological cationic species like biogenic polyamines. Even though the polyamines interact with many biomolecules present in cellular media in anionic forms, the possibility that this interaction might influence the *in vivo* speciation of InsP₆ has been scarcely explored.

Figure 1. (a) Structure of 1 axial-5 equatorial (1a5e) and 5 axial-1 equatorial (5a1e) phytate conformations. (b) Structure of the studied biogenic polyamines.

For this reason, we determined the stability constants of the relevant InsP₆-amine adducts, at 37.0 °C and 0.15 M ionic strength. The employed biogenic amines are those depicted in Figure 1b, while the synthetic models of longer polyamines are 1,19-dimethyl-1,4,7,10,13,16,19-heptaazanonadecane (Me₂hexaen), 1,22-dimethyl-1,4,7,10,13,16,19,22-octaazadocosane (Me₂heptaen), 1,25-dimethyl-1,4,7,10,13,16,19,22,25-nonaazapentacosane (Me₂octaen) and tripropylene-tetraamine (tripen). The free energy and the enthalpic and entropic contributions were measured by means of isothermal titration calorimetry, and DFT calculations were performed on some of the detected species.

The potentiometric study showed a strong association between the anionic forms of InsP₆ and the protonated species of polyamines. The complexes detected have 1:1 and 2:1 amine:phytate stoichiometries in different states of protonation and are stable enough to

compete with the major biological metal ions for the phytate. The speciation for a simulated intracellular scenario shows that, even though the phytate is still associated with magnesium (above 33 %), the InsP_6 -polyamines complexes are significantly abundant.

In general, protonated forms of the amines associate more strongly in solution with more deprotonated forms of InsP_6 , in line with an electrostatic model of interaction. Some found exceptions to this model illustrate interesting structural aspects of the molecular recognition: the most charged and rigid species of the longest polyamines seem to be less able to match the binding sites of InsP_6 anions. Besides, the complex stability increases with polyamine length because of the rise in the number of hydrogen bond contacts and flexibility.

Increasing the length and the number of nitrogen atoms of the polyamines causes an increment in the number of exothermic complexation equilibria. Exothermic associations are endoentropic, while endothermic reactions are exoentropic, showing that strong binding interactions ($\Delta H^\circ \ll 0$) correspond to entropy loss, while weaker binding interactions ($\Delta H^\circ \geq 0$) produce favourable entropic contributions. The computational analysis shows that in the 1:1 species, the amines approach the 1a5e phytate conformation *syn* to the phosphate at C2, setting up a network of $-\text{N}-\text{H}\cdots\text{O}-$ and $-\text{N}\cdots\text{H}-\text{O}-$ hydrogen bonds, mediated by the solvent molecules (Figure 2). The second amine in the 2:1 complexes seems to be linked to the other side of the ring. The calculated structural parameters are in line with the stability of the studied species, and reinforce the idea that the thermodynamic results are modulated by a subtle combination of effects coming from breaking and formation of bonds, involving the interacting partners and many solvent molecules.

Figure 2. RB3LYP/LANL2DZ geometries for the 1:1 (a) and 2:1 (b) Put- InsP_6 species. The $\text{O}-\text{H}\cdots\text{N}$ and $\text{O}-\text{H}\cdots\text{O}$ hydrogen bonds are shown as dashed and dotted lines, respectively, with the associated distances for the former in Å. Color code: C (grey), H (white), O (red), P (orange), N (blue).

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Pra1, a zincophore from *Candida albicans* kidnaps Zn^{2+} from the host – the first thermodynamic insight

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The aim of this work is to understand the interactions of Zn^{2+} with Pra1, a zincophore from *Candida albicans*, the most common cause of fungal infections in humans. Although usually a commensal fungus, it is the most common cause of candidiasis – a condition that encompasses infections that range from superficial, chronic to systemic and potentially life-threatening candidemia [1]. One significant difference in the metabolism of this fungus and the metabolism of the host that can be aimed at when looking for possible selective therapeutics is the uptake of zinc, crucial for the fungal survival and virulence. *Candida albicans* relies on a recently discovered mechanism of zinc uptake, based on a 299 amino acid secreted protein, which specifically binds Zn^{2+} , Pra1 (a so-called “zincophore”), which can uptake this metal from the environment and re-associate with the fungus via a co-expressed, genetically-linked membrane transporter, Zrt1 [2].

Scheme 1. Schematic model of *C. albicans* zinc scavenging from host cells. After invasion of the host cell, Pra1 is expressed and secreted. It binds zinc either in the form of free Zn^{2+} or from zinc-binding proteins of the host. Reassociation with *C. albicans* cell surface and Zn^{2+} transport into the cell occurs via a Pra1-Zrt1 interaction.

In the long run, we plan to understand the bioinorganic chemistry of this process, to point out the Zn^{2+} binding sites in both Pra1 and Zrt1 and understand the thermodynamics of the Pra1- Zn^{2+} -Zrt1 interaction. In this work, we point out two specific Zn^{2+} binding sites in Pra1 and discuss the binding mode and thermodynamic properties of complexes of those two regions with Zn^{2+} and Co^{2+} , an extremely useful spectroscopic probe for Zn^{2+} .

Mass spectrometry confirmed the stoichiometry of the complexes, potentiometric and calorimetric studies gave us the partial and overall stability constants and a detailed comparison of these results will make us understand which protein fragment binds Zn^{2+} and

Co²⁺ with the highest affinity, giving an indication which part of Pra1 is responsible for the binding of zinc. In order to precisely identify the binding sites, donor atoms and coordination geometry of complex species formed in solution, several spectroscopic techniques were used. The results are not only the first step towards understanding the inorganic biochemistry of zincophores, biologically relevant molecules, but they might at some point be a stepping stone towards finding new, fungus-specific treatments based on parts of zincophores coupled with an imidazole- or triazole- based antifungal drugs.

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Copper(II) L-arginate complexes as mimic of natural antibiotic – netropsin

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Complexes including (S)-2-amino-5-guanidinopentanoic acid, commonly known as L-arginine, are characterised by very good antibacterial and antifungal properties [1-3]. The presence of a guanidine group in the structure of L-arginine, causes L-arginine, and its complexes with metal ions, are considered as two natural analogue antibiotics – *netropsin* and *distamycin* (Fig. 1). Both complexes are highly selective in binding with DNA regions rich in A-T pairs and are active anticancer and antiviral substances. Binding tightly to B-DNA, *distamycin* and *netropsin* penetrate minor groove and hinder the activity of polymerases. Both antibiotics are cytotoxic in vitro and in vivo to Ehrlich and Walker tumors. Netropsin inhibits the growth of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and the proliferation of animal viruses. *Distamycin* inhibits the synthesis of viral DNA *Herpes simplex*. An important aspect in the search for new antibiotics and higher generations of anticancer drugs is the development of binds' models, determine the preferred locations in the DNA, which

Fig. 1. The structure of netropsin and L-arginine complexes [1-3].

combines / intercalates the potential antibiotic or cytostatic. Therefore, research on the understanding of the impact of ions of simple salts, protein structures of nucleic acids and the analysis of the effects of structural changes in the genetic material are of continuing interest. A particular analogue of netropsin in binding to AT-DNA are the complexes of the formula [Cu(L-Arg)₂](NO₃)₂ and [Cu(L-Arg)(phen)Cl]Cl·2,5H₂O (Fig. 1) [1-2]. As research indicates that these complexes efficiently bind to DNA and participate in its photo-induced decomposition during irradiation of

UV-A and red light. The preliminary studies that we have carried out showed that the complex {[Cu(L-Arg)₂(4,4'-bpy)]Cl₂·3H₂O}_∞ is slightly cytotoxic and has a very good bactericidal and fungicidal properties [4]. In addition to the microbiological analysis of the activity of compound {[Cu(L-Arg)₂(4,4'-bpy)]Cl₂·3H₂O}_∞, we conducted a preliminary anti-microbial study of the two newly-

obtained L-arginine compounds of formula $[\text{Cu}(\text{L-Arg})(\text{NCS})_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L-Arg})_2(\text{NCS})]\text{NCS}$ (Fig. 2). The results of microbiological tests of pilot tests give a chance to get the next in a series of compounds with anti-microbial properties and are protected by intellectual property rights in a form of patent applications [5].

Fig. 2. The crystal structure of a) $[\text{Cu}(\text{L-Arg})(\text{NCS})_2]$ and b) $[\text{Cu}(\text{L-Arg})_2(\text{NCS})]\text{NCS}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complexes.

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Coordination properties of new oxime-containing Schiff base ligand towards nickel(II), zinc(II) and copper(II) ions

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Coordination polymers and grid complexes are structures created as a result of self-assembly of polynuclear complexes. The design of such systems requires the use of algorithms covering most advantageous coordination geometry of the metal ion coordination and ligand binding sites [1].

Coordination polymers are defined as infinite systems composed of two basic elements, which are organic ligands and metal ions linked with coordination bond and other weaker interactions. These compounds impress not only the diversity of structures that are created, but most of all they are a group of materials with various properties. Research on the potential application consists primarily of magnetic and optical properties [1].

Grid complexes are complex systems containing metal ions maintained in a scaffold formed by organic ligands arranged perpendicularly. They are very popular because of their interesting magnetic, electronic and photophysical properties [2]. They are considered as potential molecular storage media in the age of miniaturization of electronic devices [3].

The studies of grid complexes in solution are challenging, and there are limited data in the literature. However, they are a necessary complement to the crystallographic data and magnetic measurements. Here we propose a new polynucleative ligand with the ability to self-assembly. The studies performed include a full physico-chemical and crystallographic characterization of 2-[1-(3,5-dimethyl)pyrazolyl]-2-hydroxyimino-N'-[1-(2-pyridyl)ethylidene]aceto-hydrazide (Hpoap) (Scheme 1) containing several donor functions of different nature towards nickel(II), zinc(II) and copper(II) ions and its ability to aggregate.

Scheme 1. Hpoap

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Template synthesis of iron and cobalt(II) (per)fluorocathrochelates with superhydrophobic exterior.

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Bulky ribbed substituents, such as adamantyl, long-chain paraffin, perfluoroalkyl, pfluoroaryl and (per)fluoroarylsulfide, in macrobicyclic encapsulating ligands of cage metal complexes (clathrochelates) are described [1–4] to form second hydrophobic and superhydrophobic shells around a caged metal ion, thus allowing for membrane transport and target delivery of clathrochelates to a given biological system. We have obtained new *n*-butyl-, phenyl- and pentafluorophenylboron-capped iron and cobalt(II) tris-perfluoro- α -benzylidioximates (Scheme) *via* template condensation of three molecules of weakly coordinating perfluoro- α -benzylidioxime with corresponding boronic acids on Fe^{2+} and Co^{2+} ions as a matrix. The complexes obtained were

Figure

characterized using elemental analysis, MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry, IR, UV-Vis, ^1H , ^{11}B , ^{13}C and ^{19}F NMR spectroscopies and by X-ray diffraction. In these complexes, the second superhydrophobic shell around a caged metal ion (Figure) is formed by fluorine atoms of both the apical and ribbed fluoroaryl terminal groups.

The synthesis of these cage complexes was

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Vancomycin and its metal complexes

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Vancomycin is the prototypical glycopeptide antibiotic commonly used as a front line treatment for infections caused by methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) but is losing a battle against a growing number of resistant bacteria [1]. Therefore there is an urgent demand for antimicrobial agents effective against multi-drug resistant bacteria [2]. Recently it has been demonstrated that silver ions can enhance vancomycin bioactivity in vitro and in vivo against Gram-negative bacteria, thereby expanding the antibacterial spectrum of this drug [3]. Thus, it is imperative to investigate the possible interactions of metal ions with glycopeptides from the vancomycin family, to understand the mode of action of those metal complexes, and their effect on bioactivity in biological systems. Although vancomycin and teicoplanin form stable complexes with copper ions, the role of metal ions in the pharmacology of those antibiotics is unknown [4]. We now report on an examination of the copper and silver ion-vancomycin complexes using isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC). The copper ion was found to possess very weak binding affinity to vancomycin. Then we have examined the interactions of silver with peptide ligands containing the DALa-DALa motif and silver's effects on the binding affinity of vancomycin with the ligands. Vancomycin is known to inhibit peptidoglycan biosynthesis by binding to the DALa-DALa dipeptide component of the precursor Lipid II. There was no interaction between silver and any tested ligand, and thermodynamics values from silver ions titrated into ligand-vancomycin complexes were identical to those from experiments with silver ion titrated into vancomycin alone. At the current stage, our results add to the preliminary evidence supporting the application of silver ion as antibiotic adjuvant to develop more efficient and sophisticated therapies and to offer a potential new approach towards treating the threat of 'superbugs'.

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